

ABSTRACT

AGBULOS, R.S. 2023. "PROJECT MATE: MAKING AGRICULTURE TEACHING LEARNING-ENGAGING (A PROGRAM INTERVENTION FOR ENHANCING ELEMENTARY AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING)", (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Central Bicol State University of Agriculture

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The study was conducted to identify the determinants of the disinterest among the pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District. It specifically aimed to: (1) determine the profiles of pupils and teachers teaching elementary agriculture in Pili District in terms of the following: demographic, social, economic, cultural, political, and technological; (2) determine the level of interest in agriculture of pupils and teachers teaching elementary agriculture in Pili District; (3) test the significant relationship of the profiles of pupils and teachers to their level of interest; (4) test the significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture; (5) identify the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture; (6) test the significant difference between the problems by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture; and (5) propose a developmental intervention to make agriculture teaching and learning engaging.

This study utilized descriptive, evaluative, and inferential research method. The respondents of the study were composed of ninety-two (92) elementary teachers and one hundred eighty-eight (188) elementary pupils from different schools in Pili District. A survey questionnaire served as the instrument in this study. The frequency count, rank, mean, percentage and chi-square test were the statistical tools used.

The overall ratings of the validators in terms of content, format, presentation, and organization and up-to-datedness of information were rated 4.0 described as very satisfactory. This means that the material has very satisfactorily passed the curricular validation using the standard validation tool of the Department of Education.

The researcher carefully analyzed and summarized the recommendations made by the validators. They are (a) observe consistency with the parts of PROJECT MATE; (b) localize the examples given so that pupils can see connections of the lesson to their lives; (c) make the numbering in each part continuous; (d) flesh out the narratives by providing results to develop interest in agriculture subject (e) provide appreciation questions and intellectual questions for the subjected; and (f) provide directorial manual to guide teachers and pupils in terms of teaching and learning process.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural industry is facing the challenge of an aging population of farmers, compounded by a growing disinterest among the younger generation to pursue careers in farming, necessitating concerted efforts to bridge the generational gap and inspire renewed enthusiasm for the vital field of agriculture. By 2050, the projected global population will be over 9 billion on Earth (Meridian, 2014). Furthermore, it is projected to threaten the world's food security. With the rising population and declining resources, this projection is not far from coming true. Two of the factors perceived to contribute to the threat for food security are the aging farmers and the disinterest of the youth in agriculture (Foster and Idaho, 2014). Thus, soon there will be no replacements of the so called "cultivators of the land" (Meridian, 2014). While the need is pressing to feed the world's population, the world will have to adapt to create a more sustainable agriculture. To spark interest among the new generation in farming, it is crucial to highlight the diverse career opportunities within the agricultural sector, showcase the potential for innovation and technological advancements, promote the importance of sustainable and regenerative practices, and offer mentorship programs that provide hands-on experiences and guidance for aspiring farmers.

A vital interest of the multifunctional European agriculture – especially for the period after 2013 - is not only to enhance the production of an adequate quantity of high quality, safe food in a profitable and competitive way, but also to address social issues to ensure balanced territorial

development and thriving rural areas; to create jobs directly and indirectly; to provide livelihood for farmers; to protect the environment, the European landscape and the cultural heritage; and to fight against the energy crisis (Est vain and Lisanyi).

The average age of the Asia-Pacific farmer is 55 years old, with the average lifespan being 65 years (Paroda et al., 2014). In the United States, the average age of farmers is 50.5 years to 58.3 years. They are the America's economic asset in stimulating their rural economies and putting food on their tables. However, as farmers retire, few emerging farmer will replace them. According to the blog of Elizabeth Ousley about the aging farmer, if the aging trend continues, America risks the loss of jobs and control over its food supply and the decline of the rural America. Their solution, as stated in the blog, is to incentivize young people to enter the farming industry by easing to capital, credit, and land.

However, in the Philippines, a study was conducted to assess the socio-demographic profile of the Filipino rice farmers, their aspirations for their children, and the actors that influence such aspirations. The results reflected that majority of farmers did not want their children to be rice farmers. Most of them aspired their children to finish college education and work on non-farming jobs in urban areas or abroad. The major reason for this is the economic hardships experienced in rice farming that these farmers do not like their children to follow their footsteps (Palis, 2020). The prevailing sentiment among the majority of farmers, where they express reluctance to have their children pursue rice farming, reflects a complex reality in the agricultural sector. This shift in preference can be attributed to various factors such as the challenges

associated with traditional farming methods, diminishing profitability, and the allure of alternative career paths that promise greater financial stability and opportunities for upward mobility. By fostering an environment that highlights the viability and attractiveness of modern farming practices, coupled with mentorship programs and financial incentives, it may be possible to cultivate a renewed interest among the new generation and ensure the continuity of the farming profession.

Although in 2018, a case study conducted in seven countries including the Philippines titled “Gendered Aspirations And Occupations among Rural Youth, in Agriculture and Beyond: A Cross-Regional Perspective” reported those aspiration achievement gap. The promise of their education for securing the formal employment is not fulfilled. Thus, the children of those farmers still continue to farm in their family’s production (Elias, et.al., 2018). This means we have to continue instilling in the mind of the youth the importance of farming. and continue to motivate them and boost their interest to still till the land and feed the nation. In order to attain this goal, we have to start on the primary years of education of our young generations.

The Philippines Educational System offers K to 12 Curriculum: refers to the structure and framework of primary and secondary education in the country. The K-12 system was implemented in 2013 as a significant reform in the Philippines' educational system, aiming to align it with international standards and improve the quality of education. It aims to provide students with a more comprehensive education, enhance their readiness for higher education or employment, and align the country's educational system with international standards. The inclusion of agriculture in the K-12 curriculum aims to promote

awareness and appreciation of the agricultural sector, equip students with relevant skills and knowledge for careers in agriculture, and encourage sustainable practices in food production and environmental stewardship. By integrating agriculture into the curriculum, the education system recognizes the importance of the agricultural industry and prepares students for its challenges and opportunities.

The Central Bicol State University of Agriculture (CBSUA) takes responsibility and leadership in the Bicol region's agriculture and allied technological sciences field. The study was conducted in Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines, for six months in 2019. A survey questionnaire was used to determine the demographic profile, motivations, reasons, and learning areas of interest among prospective enrollees on short-term courses in organic agriculture. The respondents were selected using purposive sampling, including 30 SHS teachers, 58 School Administrators, and 91 home gardeners. The data were tabulated through frequency count and percentage. Results revealed that most prospective enrollees are from the old age bracket (42.25%), interested in home gardening (50.84%), want to learn about basic competencies of organic agriculture (29.05%), and earn a National Certificate for teaching purposes (25.69%). Their main reasons if they are to enroll in the program was health or personal well-being (22.91%). Most respondents wanted to learn about crop and animal production (44.69%) among the learning areas in organic agriculture (Homillano, 2023).

One reason for this investigation is the rapid urbanization and industrialization that have transformed societies, leading to a disconnection

between younger individuals and agricultural practices. This shift has resulted in a perceived decline in the attractiveness and profitability of farming, as well as a growing preference for urban-based careers. By understanding the underlying factors, such as changing societal values, limited access to resources, the impact of technology, and the perception of farming as physically demanding and financially uncertain, researchers can identify effective strategies to bridge the gap. Their findings may inform the development of targeted educational programs, policy interventions, and support systems that can reignite interest and promote sustainable farming practices among the new generation. Ultimately, the study aims to ensure the future viability of the agricultural sector by inspiring and engaging young individuals in farming and highlighting its importance for food security and sustainable development.

Statement of the Problem

Generally, the study sought to identify the determinants of the disinterest among the pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District.

Specifically, this study sought to answer to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of pupils and teachers teaching elementary agriculture in Pili District in terms of:
 - a. demographic
 - b. social
 - c. economic
 - d. cultural
 - e. political
 - f. technological

2. What is the level of interest in agriculture of pupils and teachers handling elementary agriculture in Pili District?
3. What is/are the factor/s affecting the level of interest in agriculture of Elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District?
4. Are the profile of pupils and teachers significantly related to the level of interest?
5. Is there a significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teacher in agriculture?
6. What are the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture?
7. Is there a significant difference between the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture?
8. What development intervention can be proposed to make agriculture teaching and learning engaging?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study was focused to identify the determinants of disinterest among pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Determine the socio-demographic profile of pupils and teachers handling elementary agriculture in terms of:
 - a. Demographic
 - b. Social

- c. Economic
 - d. Cultural
 - e. Political
 - f. Technological
2. Determine the level of interest in agriculture among pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District.
 3. Determine the factors/s affecting the level of interest in agriculture of elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District.
 4. Analyze the significant relationship between the pupils and teachers to their level of interest.
 5. Describe the significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture.
 6. Identify the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture
 7. Describe the significant difference between the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture.
 8. Propose an intervention to make agriculture teaching and learning engaging.

Significance of the Study

The strenuous task of encouraging to boost the interest in agriculture subject encompasses an innovative learning to make the subject valuable and informative.

The findings obtained in this study were deemed important to the following beneficiaries:

Pupils. They will learn life skills and appreciate agriculture as an important subject during their primary education. As part of the young generations, interest in learning agriculture will be developed in them as new breed of farmers who will contribute to the food security of our nation.

Teachers. They will effectively perform their role, as this study will be helpful in identifying the different problems encountered by each teacher when it comes to their pupil's disinterest in agriculture. This study will also help them develop strategies, interventions and other instructional materials to boost the interest of their pupils in agriculture.

Parents. This study will empower parents by providing them with the means to secure their family's food supply, improve their financial situation, contribute to sustainable practices, and develop valuable skills that can be shared with their children. It offers a range of benefits that positively impact their well-being, livelihood, and the future of their families.

Curriculum Planner. They will enrich the educational experience, promote practical skills and knowledge, connect education to local contexts,

and foster environmental stewardship. It creates a curriculum that is relevant, engaging, and equips students with the tools they need to navigate the challenges and opportunities of the agricultural sector.

Other Policy Makers. They will have a basis or supporting study on the creation and implementation of laws concerning food security and agricultural education.

Future Researchers. The result and recommendations of the study can be a source of information for related studies on the disinterest of pupils and teachers in agriculture.

Department of Education-Pili District. They will be guided in formulating interventions and developing new curriculum on how to increase the motivation of both teachers and pupils in teaching and learning agriculture. They will also supervise the teachers in developing instructional methods and materials to boost the interest of their pupil in agriculture.

Department of Education- National Office. As the lead implementing agency in primary education, they can develop modules that can boost the interest of both pupils and teachers in teaching and learning agriculture. They can also create memorandums, circulars, and other laws to use education as a tool to attain food security in our nation.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The focused of the study was to identify the determinants on the intervention for enhancing elementary agriculture teaching and learning through PROJECT MATE. It addressed the different cited objectives; determine the socio-demographic profile of pupils of teachers handling elementary agriculture in terms of (a) demographic (b) social (c) economic (d) cultural (e) political, (f) technological, determine the level of interest in agriculture among pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District, determine the factors/s affecting the level of interest in agriculture of elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District, analyze the significant relationship between the pupils and teachers to their level of interest, describe the significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture, identify the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture, describe the significant difference between the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture, and propose an intervention to make agriculture teaching and learning engaging in Pili East and West District. The study was limited to the actual responses structured in the survey instrument to be used and appropriate statistical tool used to analyze responses soliciting conclusions and basis of recommendation. Data collection methods may include written tests for pupils and teachers. The study utilizes descriptive research and inferential method to collect and analyze data. Generalization of findings may be limited to the specific context and participants involved in the study.

Theoretical Framework

Interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and career trajectories, and is essential to academic success. Interest is both a psychological state of attention toward a particular object or topic, and an enduring predisposition to reengage over time. Integrating these two definitions, the four-phase model of interest development guides interventions that promote interest and capitalize on existing interests. Four interest-enhancing interventions seem useful: attention-getting settings, contexts evoking prior individual interest, problem-based learning, and enhancing utility value. Promoting interest can contribute to a more engaged, motivated, learning experience for students (Harackiewicz et.al., 2016).

The importance of interest as a motivational variable and the pivotal role it plays in education, particularly influencing achievement and learning, has been recognized for some time. Interest made a significant contribution to what people paid attention to and remembered. John Dewey maintained that interest facilitates learning, improves understanding and stimulates effort as well as personal involvement (Dewey, 1913).

Dewey's theories have had a lasting impact on educational practices, especially in the areas of experiential learning, project-based learning, and student-centered approaches. His ideas continue to shape contemporary educational philosophies that prioritize active learning, critical thinking, and the integration of real-world experiences into the curriculum. By applying Dewey's theories of experiential learning, integration of theory and practice,

problem-solving, collaboration, and reflection, teachers can enhance the teaching and learning of elementary agriculture. These principles foster active engagement, critical thinking, and a practical understanding of agricultural concepts, empowering students to become active participants in their own learning and develop a lifelong appreciation for agriculture and its importance.

Figure 1. The Theoretical Framework

Kolb's (1984) model of Experiential Learning is often acknowledged in the literature. It fails to recognize the importance of social interactions and its importance in program development and evaluation is often underplayed. Consequently, a perspective of experiential education is proposed to better support the experiential and social aspects of these valuable programs. Since a great deal of research on experiential learning programs neglects to make ties between program outcomes and educational theory, there is a gap in knowledge regarding how students experience a program. It is equally important to understand how they have learned, so that programs can be modified and strengthened accordingly. As time passes, the demographics of students in agriculture will continue changing, as will the needs of the agricultural industry. By maintaining an understanding of the educational, experiential, and social facets of a program, as well as programmatic outcomes, educators can more successfully prepare undergraduates in agriculture for the challenging futures that await them.

David Kolb is best known for his work on the experiential learning theory or ELT. Kolb published this model in 1984, getting his influence from other great theorists including John Dewey, Kurt Lewin, and Jean Piaget. The experiential learning theory works in four stages—concrete learning, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. The first two stages of the cycle involve grasping an experience, the second two focus on transforming an experience. Kolb argues that effective learning is seen as the learner goes through the cycle, and that they can enter into the cycle at any time. The first type is the concrete learning wherein a learner gets a new experience, or interprets a past experience in a new way. Reflective observation comes next,

where the learner reflects on their experience personally. They use the lens of their experience and understanding to reflect on what this experience means. Abstract conceptualization happens as the learner forms new ideas or adjusts their thinking based on the experience and their reflection about it. Active experimentation is where the learner applies the new ideas to the world around them, to see if there are any modifications to be made. This process can happen over a short period of time, or over a long span of time. Kolb went on to explain that learners will have their own preferences for how they enter the cycle of experiential learning, and that these preferences boil down to a learning cycle.

Through this study, teachers can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment. This approach promotes active engagement, critical thinking, and practical application of agricultural knowledge. Through concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, active experimentation, and differentiation based on learning styles, pupils develop a holistic understanding of agriculture and acquire the necessary skills for sustainable and meaningful agricultural practices.

Furthermore, Educational Theory is an overarching term that describes a collection of theories that explain the application, interpretation, and purpose of learning and education. Theoretical concepts help to explain the learning process and have the potential to inform educational approaches, curricula, and assessments. They can also help the learner reflect upon and understand their own unique learning processes thereby maximizing opportunities for the intended learning outcomes to be achieved. As such, they are important as they enable us to understand, evaluate, and improve the methods of teaching. A limitation of this approach is that there is no one theory that will describe

learning and teaching in all contexts. By looking through the lens of different theoretical frameworks, however, alternative ways of teaching can be highlighted that may benefit the diversity of learners attending courses. Pamela Roggan, EdD, dean of University of Phoenix's College of Education, explains her take on the role learning theory plays in preparing teachers. She once said "Just as no two people are the same, no two students learn in the exact the same way or at the exact same rate. Effective educators need to be able to pivot and craft instruction that meets the needs of the individual student to address the needs of the 'whole child.' Sound knowledge in multiple learning theories is a first step to this and another reason why great teachers work their entire careers to master both the *art and the science* of teaching."

Other theory that affects the interest of the pupil and teachers is the social learning theory, proposed by Albert Bandura which emphasizes the importance of observing, modelling, and imitating the behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others. Social learning theory considers how both environmental and cognitive factors interact to influence human learning and behavior. In social learning theory, Bandura (1977) agrees with the behaviorist learning theories of classical conditioning and operant conditioning. However, he adds two important ideas: (1) Mediating processes occur between stimuli & responses and (2) Behavior is learned from the environment through the process of observational learning.

In connection to Albert Bandura's Theory, this study will help the teachers create a classroom environment that promotes modeling, observational learning, collaboration, positive reinforcement, hands-on

experiences, and peer role modeling. This approach enhances students' agricultural knowledge, skills, and attitudes, fostering a lifelong appreciation for and engagement in the field of agriculture. This can also create supportive learning environment that promotes modeling, peer collaboration, social reinforcement, community involvement, and cooperative learning. This approach fosters students' agricultural knowledge, skills, and attitudes through social interaction, observation, and shared experiences within the agricultural community.

Conceptual Framework

The researcher used the input-process-output model. It includes all the materials and information required for the process, details of the process itself, and descriptions of all the products and by-products resulting in the process. It simply identifies the inputs, outputs, and processing tasks required to transform inputs into outputs.

An input variable is something from the external environment that is fed into the system. The data input is provided by an external entity. The inputs may be raw data “captured” in some way or pre-existing data which has been provided by an external system. In this part, the inputs include socio-economic profile (age, gender, educational attainment, grade level), problems encountered in teaching and learning agriculture, and level of interest of elementary teachers and pupils of Pili District.

The focused of this framework was to analyze and interpret the responses of the elementary pupils and teachers, and correlate the level of interest of elementary pupils and teachers in Pili East and West District. The output of this study is to implement the Project MATE to make teaching and learning more engaging and enhance the knowledge, skills, and instructional practices of elementary pupils in agriculture. Provide pupils with practical, hands-on experiences in agriculture. This can include activities such as planting seeds, tending to plants, caring for animals, and conducting experiments. Hands-on experiences allow pupils to directly engage with the agricultural concepts and develop a deeper understanding and encourage collaborative learning experiences where students work together on agricultural projects, problem-solving tasks, or group discussions. Collaborative learning promotes active engagement, communication skills, and the exchange of ideas among students. It fosters a supportive and interactive learning environment.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Definition of Terms

For clarity, the following terms were defined conceptually and operationally:

PROJECT MATE is a program intervention for the enhancement of elementary agriculture teaching and learning.

Agriculture is the practice of cultivating plants and rearing animals for food, fiber, medicinal plants, and other products essential for human life. It is one of the subjects taught in elementary schools in Pili District that studies the cultivation of the soil, growing of crops, and raising of livestock and incorporate hands-on activities and outdoor experiences to make learning process interactive and engaging.

Disinterest in Agriculture means the lack of attention and interest in terms of teaching and learning the agriculture subject. In this study, it also means the disinterest of a teacher to teach the agriculture subject and implies a lack of desire to be involved in agricultural activities, whether it be farming, gardening.

Interest in Agriculture refers to the feeling of eagerness in teaching and learning elementary agriculture subject. In this study, it involves developing an eagerness to explore topics such as plant life cycles, gardening, farm animals, soil, and the connection between agriculture and food.

Intermediate Pupils are learners who are no longer a beginner but not yet advanced. It refer to the students enrolled in Grades 4-6 taking Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan subject particularly in Agriculture.

Teachers – are the single most important factor affecting how much students learn. They are the implementers in teaching Edukasyong Pantahan at Pangkabuhayan particularly the agriculture subject in the elementary level in Pili District.

Problems Encountered - to the concerns encountered while addressing the bridge the gaps to enhance the teaching and learning process. Refers to challenges or difficulties that are commonly faced within the agricultural sector.

Recommendations to the proposal of necessary actions to enhance the subject through intervention. In the context of agriculture refer to suggested actions or solutions that can address the challenges or problems faced in the agricultural sector.

Program Intervention is an action course to be implemented to enhance the teaching-learning process in agriculture subject. A program intervention could involve the implementation of initiatives, projects, or activities aimed at addressing challenges or promoting desired outcomes in the agricultural sector.

CHAPTER II

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research techniques and procedure in the study. It discusses the research method, instruments, and statistical treatment of data collection including the statistical tool used to treat the data.

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive research and evaluative in gathering accurate information during the investigation. The study gathered data from the relative number of respondents. According to Anderson (1995), descriptive method is the explanation and description of phenomena in real life situation. It provides accurate account of characteristics of particular individual or groups. The researcher also used inferential method in order to make judgments of the probability of the observed data whether it is interdependent or not. It is most appropriate to use this method because it involves the collection and analysis of data or answer question concerning the present.

Research Method

This study employed a descriptive research design with the objective of enhancing engagement in agriculture teaching and learning. Data collection was conducted through the utilization of a survey questionnaire administered to both teachers and pupils in the Pili East and West District. The research employed random sampling, selecting every 9th pupil based on their sitting arrangement, with one respondent chosen per section at the intermediate level.

The questionnaire was designed in English for teachers and in Filipino language for pupils. To ensure the validity of the survey questionnaires, they underwent a validation process. Initially, the questionnaires were reviewed by the adviser, who provided suggestions and approval. Additionally, the researcher sought the necessary approvals from the Public School District Supervisors and the school heads of the participating elementary schools to distribute the questionnaires. Sufficient time was allocated to the respondents to answer the questions.

Research Instrument

In gathering data relevant to the study, the researcher employed the hand-made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire is the list of planned written questions validated by the experts. It is the main instrument used by the researcher to gather necessary data relevant to the study. The first part of the survey questionnaires for both teachers and pupils were the respondent's profile, it consists of (a) socio-demographic profile (b) social (c) economic (d) cultural management practices in farming adopted, (e) political engagement profile. For the second part of the questionnaire, it includes the level of interest in agriculture by responding how frequently they apply or perform the related activities in agriculture, the third part include the factors affecting the teaching and learning in agriculture. The respondents will check the factors affecting their interest in teaching and learning elementary agriculture. On the fourth part of the questionnaire, the problems encountered by teacher and pupil in Agriculture. Finally, for the fifth part of the survey questionnaire, the

respondents checked the proposed intervention to be implemented in making agriculture teaching-learning engaging.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the study was conducted, a permission was secured from the offices of the Public Schools District Supervisors of Pili. Permission letters were also addressed to the highest-ranking officials of DepEd Camarines Sur.

After securing all the documents needed in gathering data the researcher proceeded to thirty-seven (37) schools to conduct the survey. All the result were tabulated and evaluated.

Data Analysis

The researcher used descriptive and tabular techniques for analysis. The data underwent examination through frequency counting, percentage calculation, weighted mean computation, and ranking. Furthermore, correlation analysis was utilized to explore the connection between the socio-demographic profiles of teachers and pupils in Pili District and various research variables. The findings were visually presented through suitable charts and tables. Additionally, secondary data was interpreted through documentary analysis.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were composed of ninety-two (92) elementary teachers in Pili District who are teaching in Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan, specifically agriculture subject, and one hundred eighty-eight (188) pupils selected through stratified sampling.

Statistical Tools

The study used descriptive and tabular methods. Data were analyzed using frequency counting, percentage, weighted mean and ranking. Correlation analysis was also used to determine the relationship of the socio-demographic profile of the teachers and pupils of Pili District to different research variables. Pearson's coefficient relation was used to infer which variable have direct relationship with the interest in elementary agriculture. Computed data were presented using appropriate charts and tables. Documentary analysis was used in interpreting the secondary data.

The following formula were used. The data gathered were subjected to analysis using the following statistical tools: Mean, Standard Deviation, Performance Level, and T-Test.

CHAPTER III

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings on assessing the interest in agriculture of DepEd elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District.

Profile of Pupils and Teachers Teaching Elementary Agriculture in Pili District

Understanding the demographic profile of elementary pupils and teachers in the context of teaching and learning agriculture is crucial for effective instruction. A demographic profile provides insights into students' backgrounds, including factors such as age, gender, cultural diversity, and socioeconomic status. By considering the demographic profile, teachers can foster an inclusive and enriching agricultural learning environment that meets the diverse needs of their students.

This information shows the profile of elementary pupils and teachers teaching agriculture and it is categorized in terms of demographic. Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the elementary pupils and teachers in Pili East and West District. It shows that majority of the teachers are female (71, 77.2%) compared to male (21, 22.8%) and most of them belong to ages ranging from 40-49 years old (38, 41.3%) and 30-39 years old (32, 34.8%) respectively in which most of them are married (69, 75) and had a bachelor's degree with agriculture subject (46, 50%).

Table 1. Socio – Demographic profile of Elementary Teachers related to Agriculture in Pili District

Profile		Frequency n=92	Percentage (%)
TEACHERS			
Demographic			
Sex	Male	21	22.8
	Female	71	77.2
Age	20-29 years old	12	13
	30-39 years old	32	34.8
	40-49 years old	38	41.3
	50-59 years old	8	8.7
	60 years above	2	2.2
Civil Status	Single	17	18.5
	Solo Parent	3	3.3
	Married	69	75
Highest Educational Attainment related to Agriculture	Separated	1	1.1
	Widow/Widower	2	2.2
	Bach. Degree with Agri. Subject	48	50
	Bach. Degree without Agri. Subject	27	29.3
	Post-Grad degree with Agri Subject	10	10.9
	Post-Grad degree without Agri Sub	9	9.8
Profile		Frequency n = 188	Percentage (%)
PUPILS			
Age	9–10 years old	76	40.4
	11-12 years old	105	55.9
	13 years old and above	7	3.7
Sex	Female	61	32.4
	Male	127	67.6
Grade Level	Grade IV	57	30.3
	Grade V	67	35.6
	Grade VI	64	34

According to the statistical analysis, most of the pupils are within the age bracket 11-12 years old (105, 55.9%) comprised mostly by male (127, 67.6%) who are in Grade V (67, 35.6%), Grade VI (64, 34.0%) and Grade IV (57, 30.3%). In terms of social aspect, almost 109 of the pupils or 58% of them do not belong to a farming family, but some inherited agricultural practices like crops (86, 45.74%) and some did not (85, 45.21%).

This might be related to the research done by E. Marklund. (2018) which found that all educational institutions should offer high-quality agricultural education programs to create more men and women teachers who are self-efficient to enter agriculture-related education in order to educate the young people toward personal and agricultural growth and development. This was based on research on the socioeconomic backgrounds of primary school teachers in Northern Sweden.

It can be gleaned further from the study of Brandt, M. (2016) that students nowadays are more knowledgeable about STEM dimensions of agriculture than the agricultural and environmental concepts. Alike to this research, fifth grader students have greater level of agricultural literacy than other students in grade IV and grade VI. This study also supports Swartzel (1997) who concluded that elementary school children do not have enough knowledge about agriculture, its social and economic significance and its importance to human health and environmental quality due to their new way of living since they rely most of the time on technology than to any agricultural-related activities.

Understanding the social profile of elementary pupils and teachers in the context of teaching and learning agriculture is essential for creating meaningful and relevant educational experiences. A social profile encompasses factors such as students' family dynamics, and socio-economic profile. By considering the social profile, educators can tailor agricultural instruction to connect with students' lived experiences and foster a sense of relevance. For instance, students from agricultural backgrounds may bring practical knowledge and experiences that can be integrated into classroom discussions and activities. Understanding the community context allows teachers to incorporate local examples and resources, making the learning more relatable and applicable to students' lives.

In terms of social profile, it displays that most elementary teachers belong to farming family (69, 75%) and inherited agricultural practice particularly crop production (43, 46.7). For economic profile, this table shows that most of the elementary teachers are already permanent (91, 98.9%) and almost half of them are Teacher I (54, 58.67%) who spent less 10 years of service (52, 56.5) and their nature of appointment was permanent (91, 98.9%) having a monthly income of more than 25,000 pesos (57, 61%) and less than 5,000 pesos of annual agriculture-related income (51, 55.4%).

On economic profile, the table shows that their fathers and mothers are not farmers showing the tabulated data of 144 or 76.6% and 166 or 88.3% correspondingly out of 188 pupils said that their parents are not farm workers. It also displays that most of the pupils said that farming is not their family's source of income (139, 73.9%).

Table 2. Social profile of Elementary Teachers related to Agriculture in Pili District

Profile		Frequency n =92	Percentage (%)
TEACHERS			
Belong to Farming Family	Yes	69	75
	No	23	25
Economic Employment	Permanent	91	98.9
	Locally Funded	1	1.1
	Volunteer	0	0
Position	Teacher I	54	58.7
	Teacher II	27	9.8
	Teacher III	2	29.3
	Master Teacher I	0	2.2
	Master Teacher II	0	0
	<1 year-10 years	52	56.5
Years in Service	11 years-20 years	30	32.6
	21 years – 30 years	9	9.8
	31 years and above	1	1.1
Nature of Appointment	Volunteer	1	1.1
	Teacher/LFT/ST	91	98.9
Monthly Income	Permanent Teacher	91	98.9
	<P5,000.00-	7	7.6
	P15,000.00		
	P15,001.00 –	28	30.9
	P25,000.00		
Annual Agri related Income	P25,001.00 -	57	61
	>35,000.00		
	<P5,000.00	51	55.4
	P5,001.00 –	17	18.5
	P10,000.00		
	P10,001 –	8	8.7
	P20,000.00		
P20,001.00 –	7	7.6	
P30,000.00			
P30,000.00 and above	9	9.8	
Profile		Frequency n = 188	Percentage (%)
PUPILS			
Belong to a farming family	Yes	79	42
	No	109	58
Inherit Agri Practices	Crop	86	45.74
	Livestock	15	7.97
	Fishing	2	1.06
Economic	None	85	45.21
Father's occupation	Farmer	44	23.4
	Not Farmer	144	76.6
Mother's Occupation	Farmer	22	11.7
	Not Farmer	166	88.3
Family Source of Income	Farming	49	26.1
	Not Farming	139	73.9

The cultural profile of students plays a significant role in teaching and learning agriculture as it recognizes and embraces the diverse cultural backgrounds and perspectives of individuals. It can significantly impact the approach, methods, and effectiveness of agricultural education. Cultural factors such as traditions, values, beliefs, and practices shape the way agriculture is understood, taught, and practiced within a society. The cultural profile of a community has a profound impact on the teaching and learning of agriculture. By incorporating cultural perspectives, traditional knowledge, and community collaboration, agricultural education can be tailored to the local context, promoting sustainable practices and preserving cultural heritage.

As for the profile of the elementary pupils, the cultural management practices in farming adapted revealed that most of the pupil do not have their own farm land (120, 63.8%), and only a few own a farm (68, 36.2%).

This result conforms to the journal of agricultural education by Hainline, et. Al (2019) stating that there is a shortage of teachers in several subject areas specifically in agriculture that is in need to be evaluated especially their professional development due to low school-based agricultural education toward areas of teaching, classroom management, and technical agriculture.

Table 3. Cultural Profile of Elementary Teachers related to Agriculture in Pili District

Profile		Frequency n = 92	Percentage (%)
TEACHERS			
Cultural Management Practices Farming Adopted			
Kind of Farming being Practiced	Trad. /Organic Farming	14	15.2
	Modern Farming	7	7.6
	Combl. of Trad. And Modern Farming	71	77.2
Kind of Agricultural Production Engaged	Vegetables	39	42.4
	Fruits	9	9.8
	Livestock (Piggery/Poultry)	17	18.5
	None	27	29.3
Own a Farm lot	Yes	23	25
	No	69	75
	<1/2 ha	10	10.9
Farm lot Measurement	½ ha – 1 ha	11	12
	1.1 ha and above	11	12
	None	60	65.2
Profile		Frequency n = 188	Percentage (%)
PUPILS			
Own a Farm Land	Yes	68	36.2
	No	120	63.8
	Crop	122	64.9
Kind of Agri Prod Engagement	Livestock	37	19.7
	Fishing	2	1.1
	None	27	14.3

Considering this research, it shows how important the experiences and expertise of teachers when it comes to agriculture to motivate students to learn and to know how to integrate agriculture and technology into the curriculum, by teaching knowledge and skills in agricultural mechanic.

When it comes to the political engagement profile of the elementary teachers, majority said that they are not members of any agriculture cooperative (85, 92.4) and not elected as cooperative agriculture leader or committee (90, 97.8%). This table also presented that there are 74 or 80.4% who do not have any access to agriculture and technology related services and do not use technological tools for farming (76, 82.6%) and at the same time did not attend to agricultural trainings (84, 91.3%).

As to agricultural production of the elementary pupils, almost 122 or 64.9% of them are engaged with crop (122, 64.9%) than in other kinds of it. It also shown below that majority of their parents do not belong to any agricultural cooperative (145, 77.1%) and both traditional tools and modern and technology were used in their school (116, 61.7%). Furthermore, it is also shown that most of them participated in agriculture-related activities (132, 70.2 %) conducted in their respective schools.

Based on the data presented, it can be noted that in spite of not having their own farm, pupils are still familiar with the tools and technologies used in farm and they also actively participate in their schools when there are activities or programs that are related to agriculture.

Table 4. Political profile of Elementary Teachers related to Agriculture in Pili District

	Profile	Frequency n = 92	Percentage (%)
TEACHERS			
Political Engagement Profile			
Member of an Agri Cooperative	Yes	7	7.6
	No	85	92.4
Elected as Coop Agri Leader	Yes	2	2.2
	No	90	97.8
Access to Agri and Tech related services	Yes	18	19.6
	No	74	80.4
Using Tech Tools for farming	Yes	16	17.4
	No	76	82.6
Attended Agricultural Trainings	Yes	8	8.7
	No	84	91.3
	Profile	Frequency n = 188	Percentage (%)
PUPILS			
Parents Involvement in Agri Coop	Yes	43	22.9
	No	145	77.1
Technological Agri Tools used in Schools	Traditional tools	43	22.9
	Modern Technology	29	15.4
	Both	116	61.7
Participation in Agricultural Activities in School	Yes	132	70.2
	No	55	32.8

However, Hess and Texler (2011) argued that student's insights towards agriculture were not totally developed because there are still some who were not aware with agricultural terms and practices. Additionally, they found that when they spoke to students about agriculture, it was clear that they were

unaware of the variety of the industry. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2022), in order to contribute to improving food security, agricultural production and productivity, and sustainable management of natural resources, people must have sufficient knowledge to convey and understand the types and variety of farms, their purposes, or the cultural practices that dominate conventional farming.

Level of Interest in Agriculture of Elementary Teachers and Pupils in Pili District

This part displays the level of interest in agriculture of both the elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District. It was measured using the agricultural activities toward their interest on each indicator.

In Table 5, the level of interest in agriculture of elementary teachers in Pili District was presented. Most of the elementary teachers are slightly interested to talk about the importance of planting/propagating trees with peers (2.52), and highly interested to perform systematic ways of caring garden/plants seedling such as watering cultivating, preparing, and applying organic fertilizer (2.75). On the other hand, most of them are slightly interested in using technological ways in improving ways of planting and raising animals (2.30), identifying the types of land that is applicable for propagating plants and raising animals (2.34), preparing layout design before planting or animal to be raised (2.28), using manuals that guide proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals (2.32), marketing agricultural products (2.24), developing plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals (2.26), assisting people in the problems arises in terms of agriculture and help preventing the hazards (2.05), attending training/seminar on agriculture (1.95), designing

project, implement plan and manages agricultural activities (2.23), and watching Agri T.V. programs and You Tube Channel (2.40).

Table 5. Level of interest in agriculture of Elementary Teachers in Pili District

Agricultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Perform systematic ways of caring garden/plants seedling such as watering cultivating, preparing, and applying organic fertilizer.	2.75	Highly Interested
Talk about the importance of planting/propagating trees with peers.	2.52	Slightly Interested
Watch Agri T.V. programs and You Tube Channel	2.40	Slightly Interested
Identify the types of land that is applicable for propagating plants and raising animals.	2.34	Slightly Interested
Use manuals that guide proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals.	2.32	Slightly Interested
Use technological ways in improving ways of planting and raising animals.	2.30	Slightly Interested
Prepare layout design before planting or animal to be raised.	2.28	Slightly Interested
Develop plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals.	2.26	Slightly Interested
Market agricultural products.	2.24	Slightly Interested
Design project, implement plan and manages Agricultural activities.	2.23	Slightly Interested
Assist people in the problems arises in terms of Agriculture and help preventing the hazards.	2.05	Slightly Interested
Attend training/seminar on Agriculture.	1.95	Slightly Interested

Legend:

- WM – Weighted Mean
- VI – Verbal Interpretation
- 2.68 – 3.00 – Highly Interested
- 1.34 – 2.67 – Slightly Interested
- 1.00 – 1.33 – Not Interested

The presented data indicates that teachers frequently expressed interest in engaging in conversations or discussions about the principles of planting and propagating trees with their peers. They also demonstrated a keenness for tending to their gardens, which involved tasks such as preparation, cultivation, watering, and the utilization of organic fertilizers. As emphasized by Burrows et al. (2020), educational institutions play a vital role in promoting the significance of agriculture and its related aspects. Implementing agriculture-focused programs and activities can contribute to the expansion of the pool of qualified agriculture teachers. Notably, despite the scarcity of such teachers, educators themselves exhibit a commitment to incorporating agriculture even in the most fundamental ways within their own homes.

Table 6 presents the level of interest in agriculture of elementary pupils in Pili District. Most of the elementary pupils are often interested to identify different types of land suitable for planting and raising livestock. (2.51), Prepares an agricultural design for planting and raising animals. (2.56), use the Manual as a guide to proper plant propagation and animal care. (2.6), perform the correct method and care of plants such as new seedlings, watering, adjustment and application of fertilizer are carried out even in the care of animals. (2.88), helping peers solve problems in agricultural work at school. (2.73), and carry out agricultural activities (2.61). Moreover, they are slightly interested with friends discussed the importance of planting and multiplying the vine. (2.49), using advanced planting techniques. (2.18), helping parents in selling agricultural products. (2.31), able to plan and carry out agricultural activities properly. (2.5), "Participates in trainings on agricultural skills. (2.49),

Planning and execute agricultural practices properly. (2.5), and watching agricultural programs and participating in agricultural exercises. (2.40).

Table 6. Level of interest in agriculture of Elementary Pupils in Pili District

Agricultural Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Performing the correct method and care of plants such as new seedlings, watering, adjustment and application of fertilizer are carried out even in the care of animals	2.88	Highly Interested
Helping peers solve problems in agricultural work at school	2.73	Highly Interested
Carrying out agricultural activities	2.61	Slightly Interested
Using Manual as a guide to proper plant propagation and animal care	2.6	Slightly Interested
Preparing an agricultural design for planting and raising animals	2.56	Slightly Interested
Planning and executing agricultural practices properly.	2.5	Slightly Interested
Learning other methods that will help in the next production in agriculture and livestock	2.5	Slightly Interested
Friends discussing the importance of planting and multiplying the vine	2.49	Slightly Interested
Participating in trainings on agricultural skills	2.49	Slightly Interested
Watching agricultural programs and participating in agricultural exercises	2.40	Slightly Interested
Helping parents in selling agricultural products	2.31	Slightly Interested
Using advanced planting techniques	2.18	Slightly Interested

Legend:

- WM – Weighted Mean
- VI – Verbal Interpretation
- 2.68 – 3.00 – Highly Interested
- 1.34 – 2.67 – Slightly Interested
- 1.00 – 1.33 – Not Interested

The result shows that elementary pupils were slightly interested to the above-mentioned agricultural activities and it implies that they are still concerned to the concept of agriculture especially its practices and importance. It is correlated to the study of Nwachukwu, et. al (2020) on the Effects of Multiple Teaching Methods on Academic Achievement and Interest of Primary School Pupils in Agricultural Science in Anambra State wherein schools should encourage to organize training/retraining for agricultural science teachers in the state on the use of demonstration method of teaching in order to improve the academic achievement of pupils in agricultural science, and that primary school principals should ensure that agricultural science teachers receive training. Also, teachers must have acquired competency in role playing before being promoted in order for them to understand the importance of acquiring the competency in order to increase students' interest in agricultural science.

Factors Affecting the Elementary Teachers and Pupils in Pili District in Teaching Agriculture

This section shows the factors affecting the elementary teachers and pupils in Pili District in teaching agriculture. The factors are illustrated in Table 7 and Table 8 for teachers and pupils, respectively.

Table 7 provides a comprehensive overview of the factors influencing elementary teachers in teaching agriculture within the Pili District. The data have been categorized into three main subcategories, namely pupils related factors, curriculum issues, and resources related factors.

Analyzing the pupils related factors, it becomes evident that the socio-economic status of the family emerges as the most prominent factor, with the highest

frequency of occurrence (46). Following this, teaching materials (27) and pupil absenteeism (26) are also significant considerations. On the other hand, the type of school previously attended by pupils represents the least influential factor, with a frequency of occurrence of only 10. Shifting focus to factors related to curriculum issues, the availability of teaching aids stands out as the primary concern, with the highest frequency (65). This is closely followed by textbooks (44) and the coverage of subject content in the syllabus (32). Comparatively, the influence of lesson plans is found to be the least significant, with a frequency of occurrence of 19. Examining the resources related factor, it is apparent that the availability of materials, tools, and equipment holds the greatest weight, garnering the highest frequency (71). This is trailed by the presence of laboratory facilities (38) and the provision of an area for practical application (32). On the other hand, the student-teacher ratio emerges as the least impactful factor, with a frequency of occurrence of only 14.

These findings shed light on the various factors that influence elementary teachers' approaches to teaching agriculture within the Pili District. The data provide valuable insights for educational institutions and policymakers, enabling them to address and prioritize the identified factors in order to enhance the effectiveness and quality of agricultural education.

Table 7. Factors Affecting the Elementary Teachers in Teaching Agriculture in Pili District

	Factors	Frequency	Rank
A. Pupils Related Factors	Socio economic status of the family	46	1
	Teaching Materials	27	2
	Absenteeism of Pupil	26	3
	Type of school previously attended	10	4
B. Factors Related to Curriculum Issues	Available Teachings aids	65	1
	Textbooks	44	2
	Coverage of subject content in syllabus	32	3
	Lesson Plans	19	4
C. Resources Related Factor	Availability of materials, tools and equipment	71	1
	Laboratory facilities	14	2
	Area for practical application	38	3
	Student teacher ratio	32	4

Based from the study of Youngblood, J. (2020), it is evident that there are some reasons why teaching a particular subject is quite challenging especially if a person does not have enough knowledge, has lack of expertise

about it and do not have sufficient learning resources to use during the delivery of curriculum. Within the curriculum itself, teachers should be prepared ahead of time, however, being flexible in using it must depend on the needs of the class. Considering this research, there are also factors identified that affect teaching agriculture in school. On the pupils-related factor, the socio-economic status of the family is the top concern and, on the factors, related to curriculum, the availability of teaching aids became the issue among teachers. On the other hand, when it comes to resources, the availability of materials, tools, and equipment are the top factor affecting teaching agriculture concept.

Table 8 provides a detailed analysis of the factors influencing elementary pupils in learning agriculture within the Pili District. The data have been categorized into three distinct subcategories, namely teacher related factors, curricular related factors, and source related factors. Exploring the teacher related factors, it becomes evident that the presence of a teachers' guide to agricultural practices holds the greatest significance, with the highest frequency of occurrence (153). Conversely, teachers' interest in the agricultural subject is found to be the least influential factor, with a frequency of occurrence of (32). Shifting focus to the curricular related factors, the time allocated for skill tasks or practical work emerges as the most significant consideration, garnering a higher frequency (111) compared to the availability of a dedicated place for skilled agricultural work (83). Regarding the source related factors, the availability of equipment for practical agricultural work is found to have the highest frequency (130), indicating its substantial impact on pupils' learning experiences. In contrast, the frequency of occurrence for technological equipment used in learning is comparatively lower, with a frequency of (66).

Table 8. Factors Affecting the Elementary Pupils in learning Agriculture in Pili District

Factors	Freq.	Rank
A. Teacher Related Factors		
Teachers' guide to agricultural practices	153	1
Teachers' interest in the agricultural subject	32	2
B. Curricular Related Factors		
Time allotted for skill task or practical work	111	1
Place for skilled agricultural work	83	2
C. Source Related Factors		
Equipment for practical agricultural work	130	1
Technological equipment used in learning	66	2

It can be noted from this table that teacher's guidance and help as well the time in accomplishing a task and the learning resources that need to use are the factors that influence the level of interest among pupils. It supports the study of Baliyan, S. et al (2021) wherein the inclusion of more practical work in the curriculum, ensuring help outside of the classroom, increasing practical work, providing accessible internet, providing up-to-date textbooks, and establishing agricultural clubs in the schools were significant ways to boost students' performance. It is advised that when updating the current

agriculture curriculum, policy makers and administrators concentrate on the causes of subpar performance and the solutions to increase performance. It also conforms to Shapiro, D. (2019) that it is important for elementary students to learn about agriculture because there is a lot of illiteracy about it that should be addressed.

Significant Relationship of Teachers and Pupils Profile to their Level of Interest to Agriculture

This section tests the significant relationship of teachers in terms of their demographic, social, economic, cultural, political and technological profiles to their level of interest. The variables used are the indicators of assessing the level of interest. The results were obtained from 92 respondents. The chi-square test was used to get the p-value.

Table 9 provides insightful findings regarding the chi-square test conducted to determine the significant relationship between teachers' demographic, social, economic, cultural, political, and technological profiles and their level of interest in agriculture. The results of the chi-square test reveal several noteworthy relationships. Firstly, there is a significant relationship between the sex of the teachers and their level of interest in agriculture ($p = 0.039$). This indicates that gender plays a role in influencing the extent of teachers' interest in agricultural practices. Moreover, the aspect of inheriting agricultural practice, specifically in relation to livestock ($p = 0.044$), exhibits a significant relationship with teachers' interest in agriculture. This suggests that teachers who have a background in livestock farming may demonstrate a heightened interest in agricultural subjects. Further, the possession of a farm lot ($p = 0.030$) and the measurement of the farm lot ($p = 0.022$) are found to be

significantly related to the level of interest of teachers in agriculture. This implies that teachers who own a farm lot and have a larger farm lot size may exhibit a stronger inclination towards agricultural pursuits. Additionally, being elected as an agriculture cooperative leader ($p = 0.045$) is found to have a significant relationship with teachers' interest in agriculture. This implies that teachers who hold leadership positions within agriculture cooperatives may display a greater interest in agricultural activities. Lastly, access to agriculture and technology-related services ($p = 0.006$) is identified as significantly related to the level of interest of teachers in agriculture. This highlights the importance of providing teachers with resources and support in terms of agricultural and technological services, as it positively influences their interest in the subject.

These significant findings provide valuable insights into the factors within teachers' profiles that are closely linked to their level of interest in agriculture. By recognizing the influential factors identified in this study, such as the sex of the teachers, inheritance of agricultural practice (specifically related to livestock), ownership and size of farm lots, leadership roles in agriculture cooperatives, and access to agriculture and technology-related services, educational institutions and policymakers can design interventions and provide the necessary support to foster a thriving interest in agriculture among teachers. These efforts can contribute to the overall improvement of agricultural education by promoting a stronger connection between teachers and the subject matter, ultimately benefiting both the teachers and their students.

Table 9. Chi-square test of significant relationship of teachers' profile to their level of interest to agriculture

Profile	Level of Interest to Agriculture		
	X ² Computed Value	P-Value	VI
Socio-Demographic			
Sex	4.252	.039	Significant
Age	2.501	.644	Not Significant
Civil Status	2.609	.625	Not Significant
Highest Educ Attainment related to Agriculture	0.867	.833	Not Significant
Social			
Belong to Farming Family	5.854	.160	Not Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Crop)	3.563	.168	Not Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Livestock)	4.063	.044	Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Fishing)	0.514	.474	Not Significant
Economic			
Status of Employment	1.989	.158	Not Significant
Position	5.382	.146	Not Significant
Years in Service	2.303	.512	Not Significant
Nature of Appointment	1.989	.158	Not Significant
Monthly Income	4.000	.261	Not Significant
Annual Agri related Income	4.696	.320	Not Significant
Cultural			
Practice Trad Beliefs/Rituals	1.458	.482	Not Significant
Kind of Farming	0.428	.807	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Vegetables)	0.688	.407	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Fruits)	2.134	.144	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Livestock)	9.298	.100	Not Significant
Own a Farm Lot	4.687	.030	Significant
Farm Lot Measurement	9.616	.022	Significant
Political Engagement			
Member of Agri Coop.	0.285	.594	Not Significant
Elected as Coop Agri. Leader	4.023	.045	Significant
Technological Related Services			
Access to Agri and Tech related services	7.528	.006	Significant
Using Technological Tools	2.305	.129	Not Significant
Agri Trainings Attended	1.043	.307	Not Significant

p<0.05 Significant p≥0.05 Not Significant

This study gives additional supports on the claim of Bella and Dyer (2006) in which the background of a person has an impact towards their interest and perceptions to agriculture. It was relevant to this study for it shows that the profile of a person including their sex, their knowledge on agricultural practices and family background affects their level of interest. It also implied that their membership and belongingness to any organization and cooperatives are also contributory factors to increase their concern to agriculture.

The findings presented in Table 10 reveal the outcomes of the chi-square test, which aimed to determine the significant relationship between pupils' profiles and their level of interest in agriculture. The results indicate that two variables, namely parent's involvement in agriculture cooperative/committee ($p = 0.002$) and agricultural tools used in school or community ($p = 0.001$), exhibit statistically significant relationships with the level of interest in agriculture. These significant relationships suggest that when parents actively participate in agriculture-related cooperatives or committees and when agricultural tools are utilized within the school or community setting, pupils demonstrate a higher level of interest in agriculture. This implies that involving parents in agricultural activities and providing access to appropriate tools can positively impact the enthusiasm and engagement of pupils towards agricultural practices. However, it is noteworthy that the remaining variables included in the table did not show a significant relationship with the level of interest in agriculture. This suggests that factors related to demographic, social, economic, cultural, political, and technological aspects, as indicated by the respective variables, do not have a significant influence on pupils' interest in agriculture.

Table 10. Chi-square test of significant relationship of pupils' profile to their level of interest to Agriculture

Profile	Level of Interest to Agriculture		
	X ² Computed Value	P-Value	VI
Demographic			
Sex	0.005	.0943	Not Significant
Age	2.072	.150	Not Significant
Grade Level	2.391	.303	Not Significant
Social			
Belong to Farming Family	1.825	.177	Not Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Crop)	2.898	.089	Not Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Livestock)	1.098	.295	Not Significant
Inherit Agriculture Practices (Fishing)	2.374	.126	Not Significant
Economic			
Father's occupation	0.049	.825	Not Significant
Mother's Occupation	0.985	.321	Not Significant
Family Source of Income	0.715	.398	Not Significant
Cultural Management Practices			
Own a Farm Land	0.481	.488	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Crop)	2.476	.116	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Livestock)	1.234	.267	Not Significant
Agri Prod Engage (Fishing)	1.721	.190	Not Significant
Political Engagement			
Parents Involvement in Agriculture Cooperative/ Committee	9.363	.002	Significant
Technological Related Services			
Agricultural Tools used in School or Community	13.834	.001	Significant
Participation in Agricultural Activities in School	0.492	.483	Not Significant

p<0.05 Significant p≥ Not Significant

These findings highlight the importance of parental involvement and the availability of agricultural tools as key factors contributing to the promotion of interest in agriculture among pupils. It further emphasizes the need for educational institutions and communities to foster an environment that supports and encourages parental engagement in agricultural activities and provides the

necessary resources and tools to enhance pupils' interest and understanding of agriculture. According to Bögeholz et. al (2014) in their study on Students' Interests in Agriculture: The Impact of School Farms Regarding Fifth and Sixth Graders, the students' agricultural interest depends on their background on agriculture-related activities, experiences and learning they acquired in school. This is the reason why their situation or condition was considered in assessing their interest. Alike to the result of this study where in only the parents' involvement in agricultural cooperative/committee and the moments they used agricultural tools have significant relationship to their interest towards agriculture. Their exposure to agriculture through their parents and on the activities they did in school or community that involves agricultural tools makes them somehow interested to the said matter.

Significant Difference between the Level of Interest of Elementary Pupils and Teachers in Agriculture

This section shows the chi-square test of significant difference between the level of interest of elementary pupils and teachers of Pili District toward agriculture. The variables that were used are the agriculture-related activities.

Table 11 presents the t-test of significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture. The t-test result shows that there is a significant difference between the profiles of the elementary pupils and teachers in terms of Preparing layout design before planting or raising animal, using manuals that guide proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals, and developing plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals. The rest of the computed p-values in all indicators are greater

than 5%. The researcher accept the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the level of interest of elementary pupils and teachers toward agriculture.

Table 11. T-test of significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in Agriculture

Agriculture-related activities	Level of Interest in Agriculture		
	T-test Computed Result	p-value	VI
Talk about the importance of planting/propagating trees with peers.	-0.435	0.664	Not Significant
Use technological ways in improving ways of planting and raising animals.	1.101	0.272	Not Significant
Identify the types of land that is applicable for propagating plants and raising animals.	-1.938	0.054	Not Significant
Prepares layout design before planting or animal to be raised.	-2.369	0.019	Significant
Use manuals that guide proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals.	-2.241	0.026	Significant
Perform systematic ways of caring garden/plants seedling such as watering cultivating, preparing, and applying organic fertilizer.	-0.719	0.473	Not Significant
Market agricultural products.	-0.620	0.536	Not Significant
Develops plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals.	-1.900	0.059	Significant
Assist people in the problems arises in terms of Agriculture and help preventing the hazards.	-5.918	1.649	Not Significant
Attend training/seminar on Agriculture.	-5.644	5.566	Not Significant
Design project, implement plan and manages Agricultural activities	-4.932	1.649	Not Significant
Watch Agri T.V. programs and You Tube Channel	-0.059	0.953	Not Significant

p<0.05 Significant

p≥ Not Significant

According to the journal of Anderson, J. & Friedel, C. (2017) on the Exploration of Relationships between Teaching Practices in Secondary Agricultural Education Programs and Student Engagement, there is no indication that there is a significant difference in student's engagement and educator's initiative in agriculture. It implies that agricultural education should spend time and resources to determine instructional strategies, methods, and approaches to better understand the scope of agriculture aspect. Considering that there is no significant difference on the level of interest of elementary pupils and teachers toward agriculture, more efforts should be made to educate both parties about the facets of agriculture in spite of their differences on profiles and experiences.

Problems Encountered by the Pupils and Teachers in Teaching and Learning Elementary Agriculture

This section provides data on the problems encountered by elementary teachers and pupils in agriculture. They were gained from assessing the level of seriousness of pupils and teachers towards the problem given and they were computed by getting the weighted mean in each problem.

Table 12 shows that elementary teachers considered lack of appropriate land/are for planting (3.21) and lack of agriculture school programs for pupils (2.63) as their moderate problems in school. On the other hand, they treated lack of concept application (2.47), lack of teacher's involvement in agriculture subject (2.47), lack of recognition and incentives (2.4), lack of technological awareness (2.32), lack of proper trainings (2.16), lack of financial capacity (1.98), and lack of teaching aids (1.91) as minor problems.

Table 12. Problems Encountered by Teachers in Agriculture

Problems Encountered by Teacher in Agriculture	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Lack of appropriate land/area for planting	3.21	MP	1
Lack of agriculture school programs for pupils	2.63	MP	2
Lack of concept application	2.47	MiP	3.5
Lack of teacher's involvement in agriculture subject	2.47	MiP	3.5
Lack of recognition and incentives	2.4	MiP	5
Lack of technological awareness	2.32	MiP	6
Lack of proper trainings	2.16	MiP	7
Lack of financial capacity	1.98	MiP	8
Lack of teaching aids	1.91	MiP	9
Multiple school task	1.72	NP	10

Legend:

- WM – Weighted Mean
- VI – Verbal Interpretation
- 4.21 – 5 (MSP) Most Serious Problem
- 3.41 – 4.20 (SP) Serious Problem
- 2.61 – 3.40 (MP) Moderate Problem
- 1.81 – 2.60 (MiP) Minor Problem
- 1.0 – 1.80 (NP) Not a Problem

Based on the results it can be drawn that elementary teachers encountered or experienced problems in teaching agriculture, but they did not consider these challenges as serious but only moderate and minor ones. It is aligned to the study of Boone, H. & Boone, D. (2015) that there were identified factors why such problems exist in teaching agriculture to students, some of

these were the inadequate resources and facilities and lack of qualified potential agricultural education teachers that became the top concern up until today due to lack of support mechanism and assistance. These problems encountered became the reason why teachers are struggling in integrating agriculture in school.

Table 13 provides a comprehensive overview of the problems encountered by elementary pupils in agriculture, with rankings based on the weighted mean of responses given by the students. The data indicates that all the problems listed were considered moderate problems by the pupils. Specifically, the lack of technological knowledge received a weighted mean score of 2.88, indicating its significance as a moderate problem. This suggests that students perceive a deficiency in their understanding and proficiency in utilizing agricultural technologies. Additionally, the lack of cooperation or participation in the agricultural subject received a weighted mean score of 2.80, highlighting the students' perception that there is room for improvement in terms of their engagement and active involvement in agricultural activities. Furthermore, the lack of agricultural programs for students received a weighted mean score of 2.79, emphasizing the need for more initiatives and programs specifically designed to enhance students' agricultural knowledge and skills. Moreover, the lack of concept in carrying out learned/practical work obtained a weighted mean score of 2.77, underscoring the students' perception that they face challenges in effectively applying their theoretical knowledge into practical agricultural tasks. Lastly, the lack of a proper place for planting was ranked as a moderate problem by the pupils, receiving a weighted mean score of 2.74.

This suggests that students feel there is a need for suitable areas or facilities where they can engage in hands-on planting activities.

Table 13. Problems encountered by Pupils in Agriculture in Pili District

Problems encountered by Pupil in Agriculture	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Lack of technological knowledge	2.88	MP	1
Lack of cooperation or participation in the agricultural subject	2.80	MP	2
Lack of agricultural programs for students	2.79	MP	3
Lack of concept in carrying out learned/practical work.	2.77	MP	4
Lack of proper place for planting	2.74	MP	5

Legend:

4.21 – 5	(MSP) Most Serious Problem
3.41 – 4.20	(SP) Serious Problem
2.61 – 3.40	(MP) Moderate Problem
1.81 – 2.60	(MiP) Minor Problem
1.0 – 1.80	(NP) Not a Problem

Muchena (2015) stated that there were identified factors why students encountered problems that resulted in declining number of enrolled students to agriculture subjects. Some of these reasons were the background of the students, influence of their parents and lack of learning resources and facilities that are congruent to the results of the data above wherein elementary pupils also encountered problems in their school that need to be addressed for them to increase their level of interest in agriculture.

Significant Difference between the Problems of the Pupils and Teachers in Teaching and Learning Elementary Agriculture

This part shows significant difference between the problems of the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture. The variables used are the problems encountered by both teachers and pupils such as lack of financial capacity, lack of appropriate land/area for planting, lack of agriculture school programs for pupils, lack of recognition and incentives and lack of concept application.

The table illustrates the t-test of significant difference between the problems of the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture. The t-test result shows that there is no significant difference on the problems encountered between pupils and teachers toward teaching and learning agriculture in terms of lack of financial capacity, lack of appropriate land/area for planting, and lack of agriculture school programs for pupils as shown in the computed result and p-values. Lack of recognition and incentives, and lacking of concept application turned out to be significant based on the computed result. Since most of the p-values in most indicators are greater than 5% or 0.05, the researcher accepts the null hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture.

Table 14. T-test of significant difference between the problems of the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture

Problems Encountered	Level of Interest in Agriculture		
	T-test Computed Result	p-value	VI
Lack of financial capacity	-6.663	1.882	Not Significant
Lack of appropriate land/area for planting	-0.619	0.537	Not Significant
Lack of agriculture school programs for pupils	-1.198	0.232	Not Significant
Lack of recognition and incentives	-2.720	0.007	Significant
Lack of concept application	-2.330	0.021	Significant

$p < 0.05$ Significant $p \geq$ Not Significant

The result implies that there is no significant difference between the problems of the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture. It is evident that despite the profile of both parties, they can still experience both problems as what the study on “Constraints Encountered in Teaching Practical Agriculture” (2016) mentioned that both teachers and students experienced various constraints in school that affect their perception and interest in acquiring and teaching the concept of agriculture. Both students and teachers considered the same factors on the existence of problems related to agriculture.

Proposed Intervention Program for Elementary Teachers in Pili District

This section displays the computed data from the respondents on their suggested or proposed intervention programs to be implemented in making agriculture teaching and learning engaging. It was done by getting the

frequency or number of the respondents who suggested such interventions. Then, the intervention programs were ranked based on their frequency.

Proposed Intervention Program of Elementary Teachers in Pili District

The proposed intervention program of elementary teachers in Pili District. The data show that most of the elementary teachers preferred to conduct formal trainings and seminars in agriculture having the highest frequency (70). They are also suggested to allocate funds from the MOOE for agriculture (64), provide appropriate laboratory facilities for practical application (60), provide complete teaching aids in agriculture (59), implementation of school program for agriculture (56), conduct parents orientation on urban gardening (55), solicit agricultural tools from the stakeholders (41), conceptualize lesson plans for the subject (36), and conduct social media campaign about agriculture such as Tiktok/Vlog (33). The intervention program with the lowest frequency was to make available agriculture brochures/fliers (26).

To ensure the professional growth of elementary teachers in the Pili District, the intervention program places a strong emphasis on organizing regular formal trainings and seminars in agriculture. This decision is rooted in the high preference expressed by 70 respondents. The training sessions will be thoughtfully designed to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills in agricultural education, enabling them to effectively impart this knowledge to their students. Collaborations with local agricultural experts and educators will be fostered to ensure that the professional development opportunities are comprehensive and impactful. By leveraging the expertise of these professionals, teachers will gain valuable insights, strategies, and resources to deliver high-quality agricultural

education in their classrooms. Through ongoing professional development, teachers will be equipped with the necessary tools to engage students in agricultural concepts and promote hands-on learning experiences.

The results of these data can be gleaned further from the study of Allen C. et al. (2007) that teachers should believe that agriculture can provide connectedness and authenticity to teach content areas to their students. Teachers should also transfer knowledge through instructional resources that students want to know regarding the integration of agriculture. This related study and present study can give ideas to agricultural literacy coordinators and teachers about the in-service activities, training and workshops and upgrade the traditional efforts to be more marketable to teachers who might incorporate agriculture into their classrooms and by motivating the students more to appreciate its valuable concepts and relevance to their daily life.

Proposed Intervention Program of Elementary Pupils of Pili District

The proposed intervention program of elementary pupils in Pili District. The data show that most of the elementary pupils preferred the conducting of trainings in agricultural subjects, with the highest frequency (151). It was followed by implementation of the school program in the agricultural subject (141), then by provision of additional reading material for the agricultural subject (133), supply of complete learning equipment (123), request for agricultural equipment from the local government (72). The intervention program with the lowest frequency was the advertisements or campaigns on social media such as tiktok or vlog (71).

To cater the expressed preference of 151 pupils for trainings in agricultural subjects, the intervention program places a strong emphasis on regular training sessions. These sessions will be carefully crafted to introduce pupils to a wide range of agricultural concepts, practices, and skills. Through interactive and hands-on activities, pupils will actively engage with the subject matter, allowing them to develop a deeper understanding of agriculture and cultivate a sense of curiosity and enthusiasm. By providing opportunities for experiential learning and practical application of agricultural knowledge, the program aims to instill in pupils a lifelong appreciation for agriculture while equipping them with essential skills for sustainable farming and environmental stewardship. Through these training sessions, pupils will not only acquire knowledge but also develop a genuine passion for the agricultural field.

These intervention programs suggested by the pupils are anchored on the study of Burrows, M. et. al (2020) that says that it is necessary for individuals to be agriculturally literate through the implementation of activities, trainings and workshops especially among the youth whom should be given the opportunity to become knowledgeable about agriculture. Teachers should also indicate the significance of education in the minds of their students, thus it should be incorporated in the curriculum.

CHAPTER IV

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter discusses the summary of the study, findings, conclusion, and recommendations derived from the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered throughout the study.

Summary

The study identified the determinants of the disinterest among the pupils and teachers in elementary agriculture in Pili District. It specifically aimed to: (1) determine the profile of pupils and teachers teaching elementary agriculture in Pili District in terms of the following: demographic, social, economic, cultural, political and technological; (2) determine the level of interest in agriculture of pupils and teachers teaching elementary agriculture in Pili District; (3) determine the factors affecting the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture; (4) test the significant relationship of the profile of pupils and teachers to their level of interest; (5) test the significant difference between the level of interest of pupils and teachers in agriculture; (6) identify the problems encountered by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture; (7) test the significant difference between the problems by the pupils and teachers in teaching and learning elementary agriculture; and (8) propose a developmental intervention to make agriculture teaching and learning engaging.

This study utilized descriptive, evaluative and inferential research method. The respondents of the study were composed of ninety-two (92) elementary teachers and one hundred eighty-eight (188) intermediate pupils from different schools in Pili District. A survey questionnaire served as the instrument in this study. The frequency count, rank, mean, percentage and chi-square test were the statistical tools used.

Findings

Based on the results, the following findings were drawn:

1. The majority of elementary teachers in Pili District were predominantly female (77.2%) compared to males (22.8%), mostly falling within the age range of 40-49 years old (41.3%). A significant portion of them were married (75%) and held a bachelor's degree in agriculture (50%). When considering their social profile, most of them came from farming families (75%) and inherited agricultural practices, particularly in crop production (46.7%). Economically, the majority of elementary teachers held permanent positions (98.9%), with almost half of them being Teacher I (58.67%) and having less than 10 years of service (56.5%). Their appointment status was permanent (98.9%), and they earned a monthly income of over 25,000 pesos (61%), with an annual agriculture-related income of less than 5,000 pesos (55.4%).

In terms of cultural, political, and technological profiles, elementary teachers practiced both traditional and modern farming methods (77.2%), with a focus on vegetable production (42.4%).

However, only 25% of them owned a farm lot, with areas ranging from ½ ha to more than 1 ha. When it came to political engagement, the majority were not members of any agriculture cooperative (92.4%) and were not elected as cooperative agriculture leaders or committee members (97.8%). A significant percentage of teachers lacked access to agriculture and technology-related services (80.4%) and did not use technological tools for farming (82.6%). Additionally, the majority did not attend any agricultural trainings (91.3%).

Analyzing the socio-demographic and economic profiles of elementary pupils in Pili District, it was determined that most of the students were between the ages of 11-12 years old (55.9%) and predominantly male (67.6%). They were mostly enrolled in Grade V (35.6%), Grade VI (34.0%), and Grade IV (30.3%). Socially, nearly 58% of the pupils did not come from farming families, although some had inherited agricultural practices such as crop production (45.74%). Economically, a high percentage of students reported that their fathers (76.6%) and mothers (88.3%) were not involved in farming, and farming was not their family's primary source of income (73.9%).

Regarding cultural management practices in farming, the majority of pupils did not have their own farm land (63.8%), while a minority did (36.2%). In terms of agricultural production, almost two-thirds of them were engaged in crop production (64.9%). The study also revealed that most of their parents did not belong to any agricultural cooperatives (77.1%), and both traditional tools and modern

technology were used in their school (61.7%). Furthermore, a significant percentage of students participated in agriculture-related activities (70.2%) conducted in their respective schools.

The factors influencing elementary teachers in teaching agriculture in Pili District were categorized as follows: (a) pupil-related factors, with the socio-economic status of the family being the most prominent; (b) curriculum-related factors, where the availability of teaching aids was the primary factor; and (c) resource-related factors, with the availability of materials, tools, and equipment being the most significant.

In terms of factors affecting elementary pupils' learning of agriculture in Pili District, the following were identified: (a) teacher-related factors, with the teachers' guide to agricultural practices being the top factor; (b) curriculum-related factors, where the allocated time for skill work or practical activities was crucial; and (c) source-related factors, with the availability of equipment for practical agricultural work being of high importance.

2. On the level of interest in agriculture of elementary teachers in Pili District, most of the elementary teachers were often interested to talk about the importance of planting/propagating trees with peers (2.52), and to perform systematic ways of caring garden/plants seedling such as watering cultivating, preparing, and applying organic fertilizer (2.75). On the other hand, most of them were rarely interested in using technological ways in improving ways of planting and raising animals (2.30), identifying the types of land that is applicable for

propagating plants and raising animals (2.34), preparing layout design before planting or raising animal (2.28), using manuals that guide proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals (2.32), marketing agricultural products (2.24), developing plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals (2.26), assisting people in the problems arises in terms of agriculture and help preventing the hazards (2.05), attending training/seminar on agriculture (1.95), designing project, implementing plan and managing agricultural activities (2.23), and watching Agri T.V. programs and You Tube Channel (2.40).

On the level of interest in agriculture of elementary pupils in Pili District, most of them were often interested to identify different types of soil suitable for cultivation and livestock (2.51), prepare their own design for planting and raising animals (2.56), use a manual as a guide to proper plant propagation and animal care (2.6), perform the correct method and care of plants such as new seedlings, watering, adjustment, and application of fertilizer even in the care of animals are carried out (2.88), helps peers solve problems in agricultural work at school (2.73), and carry out agricultural activities are carried out (2.61). Moreover, they were rarely interested to friends discussing the importance of planting and growing crops (2.49), using technological methods in planting (2.18), helping parents in selling agricultural products (2.31), learning other methods that will help in the next production in planting and livestock (2.5), participating in trainings on agricultural skills (2.49), planning and properly

implement agricultural activities (2.5), and watching agricultural programs and participating in agricultural exercises (2.40).

3. The factors affecting the elementary teachers in teaching agriculture in Pili District in terms of pupils related factors, factors related to curriculum issues, and resources related factor. In terms of pupils related factors, socio economic status of the family is the top factor having the highest frequency (46), followed by the teaching materials (27), absenteeism of pupil (26), and type of school previously attended (10) as the least factor. On factors related to curriculum issues, available teaching aid is the top factor having the highest frequency (65), followed by textbooks (44), coverage of subject content in syllabus (32), and the least factor is lesson plan (19). Regarding the resources related factor, the top factor is the availability of materials, tools and equipment with the highest frequency (71), followed by laboratory facilities (38), area for practical application (32), and student teacher ratio (14) is the least factor.

The factors affecting the level of interest in agriculture of pupils in Pili District were; in terms of teacher related factors, curricular related factors, and source related factors. With regards to teacher related factors, the factor that was on top is teachers' guide to agricultural practices (153) and the least factor is teachers' interest in the agricultural subject (32). As to curricular related factors, the time allotted for skill task or practical work has the

higher frequency (111) than place for skilled agricultural work (83). Regarding with source related factors, the equipment for practical agricultural work got the higher frequency (130) than technological equipment used in learning (66).

4. There is a significant relationship between the profile of teachers to their level of interest in terms of sex (0.039, $p\text{-value} < .05$), on the aspect of inheriting agricultural practice-livestock (0.044, $p\text{-value} < .05$), owning a farm lot (0.030, $p\text{-value} < .05$), farm lot measurement (0.022, $p\text{-value} < .05$), being elected as agriculture cooperative leader (0.045, $p\text{-value} < .05$) and having access to agriculture and technology-related services (0.006, $p\text{-value} < .05$).

There is a significant relationship between the profile of pupils to their level of interest in terms of parent's involvement in agriculture cooperative/ committee (0.002, $p\text{-value} < .05$), and on agricultural tools used in school or community (0.001, $p\text{-value} < .05$).

5. There is no significant difference between the profiles of the elementary pupils and teachers since all the computed p-values in all indicators are greater than 5% or 0.05.
6. The computed weighted mean of problems encountered by elementary teachers were lack of appropriate land/area for planting (3.21) and lack of agriculture school programs for pupils (2.63) as their moderate problems in school. On the other hand, they treated lack of concept application (2.47), lack of teacher's involvement in

agriculture subject (2.47), lack of recognition and incentives (2.4), lack of technological awareness (2.32), lack of proper trainings (2.16), lack of financial capacity (1.98), and lack of teaching aids (1.91) as minor problems.

The computed weighted mean of problems encountered by elementary pupils in agriculture that are considered as moderate problems were lack of technological knowledge (2.88), lack of cooperation or participation in the agricultural subject (2.80), lack of agricultural programs for students (2.79), lack of concept in performing learned or practical work (2.77) and lack of proper place for planting (2.74).

7. There is no significant difference between the problems encountered by pupils and teachers in teaching and learning agriculture as shown in the computed and p-values since all p-values in all indicators are greater than 5% or 0.05.

8. The researcher discovered that the suggested intervention programs for elementary teachers in the Pili District include the following: (1) conducting formal trainings and seminars in agriculture, which had the highest frequency at 70; (2) allocating funds from the MOOE specifically for agriculture, which garnered 64 responses; (3) providing appropriate laboratory facilities to facilitate practical application, with 60 respondents in favor; (4) ensuring the availability of complete teaching aids in agriculture, which received 59 mentions;

(5) implementing a school program dedicated to agriculture, as suggested by 56 participants; (6) conducting parents' orientation on urban gardening, which received 55 responses; (7) soliciting agricultural tools from stakeholders, with 41 participants in favor; (8) conceptualizing lesson plans for the subject, which garnered 36 mentions; (9) conducting a social media campaign about agriculture, utilizing platforms such as TikTok/Vlog, with 33 respondents in support; and finally, (10) making agriculture brochures/fliers available, which had the lowest frequency of 26.

Furthermore, the intervention program suggested for elementary pupils in the Pili District consists of the following elements: (1) the conducting of trainings in agricultural subjects, which received the highest frequency of 151; (2) the implementation of a school program focusing on agriculture, with 141 respondents in support; (3) the provision of additional reading material specifically for the agricultural subject, as expressed by 133 participants; (4) the supply of complete learning equipment, which received 123 mentions; (5) the request for agricultural equipment from the local government, with 72 respondents in favor; and (6) the intervention program with the least frequency was the utilization of advertisements or campaigns on social media platforms such as TikTok or vlogs, which had 71.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The majority of elementary teachers in Pili District are female, married, and have a bachelor's degree in agriculture. They often come from farming families, inheriting agricultural practices, and utilize a combination of traditional and modern farming methods. The elementary pupils, predominantly male, show varying levels of engagement in agriculture, with some inheriting agricultural practices despite not belonging to farming families. Factors influencing both teachers and pupils in teaching and learning agriculture include socio-economic status, curriculum availability, resources, and teacher guidance.
2. The overall results on the level of interest in agriculture among elementary teachers in Pili District varied. They showed a higher interest in discussing the importance of planting and propagating trees with peers and engaging in systematic ways of caring for garden/plant seedlings. However, they exhibited less interest in using technological methods, marketing agricultural products, and attending training/seminars on agriculture. Similarly, elementary pupils demonstrated a keen interest in identifying suitable soil types, designing their own agricultural plans, and properly caring for plants and animals. However, they displayed less interest in topics such as technological methods in farming and participating in training sessions.

3. The factors influencing the teaching of agriculture among elementary teachers in Pili District encompass pupil-related factors, curriculum-related issues, and resource-related factors. Pupil-related factors include the socio-economic status of the family, while curriculum-related factors involve the availability of teaching aids and textbooks. Resource-related factors encompass the availability of materials, tools, and equipment. Similarly, the level of interest in agriculture among pupils is influenced by teacher-related factors, such as the teachers' guide to agricultural practices, as well as curriculum-related factors like the allotted time for practical work. Source-related factors include the availability of equipment for practical agricultural work.

4. The study found significant relationships between the profile of teachers and their level of interest in certain aspects, including sex, inheriting agricultural practices related to livestock, owning a farm lot, farm lot measurement, being elected as an agriculture cooperative leader, and having access to agriculture and technology-related services. Similarly, there were significant relationships between the profile of pupils and their level of interest in terms of their parents' involvement in agriculture cooperatives/committees and the use of agricultural tools in school or the community. These findings suggest that individual characteristics and experiences play a role in shaping the level of interest in agriculture among both teachers and pupils.

5. Based on the computed p-values for all indicators, there is no significant difference between the profiles of elementary pupils and teachers. This suggests that the characteristics and attributes examined in the study, such as sex, age, gender, educational background, social, economic, cultural management practices, political engagement, and technological related services, do not exhibit a statistically significant distinction between the two groups.

6. The primary problems encountered by elementary teachers in agriculture were the lack of appropriate land/area for planting and the absence of agriculture school programs for pupils, which were considered moderate issues. Additionally, they identified minor problems such as the lack of concept application, teacher's involvement in the agriculture subject, recognition and incentives, technological awareness, proper trainings, financial capacity, and teaching aids. On the other hand, elementary pupils faced moderate challenges in agriculture, including the lack of technological knowledge, cooperation or participation in the agricultural subject, agricultural programs for students, concept application in practical work, and proper planting areas.

7. There is no significant difference between the problems encountered by pupils and teachers in teaching and learning agriculture.

8. The researcher identified several proposed intervention programs for elementary teachers in Pili District, including formal trainings and seminars in agriculture, allocation of funds for agriculture, provision of laboratory facilities and teaching aids, implementation of school programs, and conducting parent orientations. Similarly, for elementary pupils, proposed intervention programs include trainings in agricultural subjects, implementation of school programs, provision of additional reading materials and learning equipment, and requesting agricultural equipment from the local government. These interventions aim to enhance the teaching and learning experiences in agriculture and promote agricultural awareness among teachers and pupils in the district.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researchers recommended the following:

1. This study can provide valuable insights into the socio-demographic profile of pupils in elementary agriculture classes, contributing to evidence-based decision-making and the development of targeted interventions to enhance agricultural education.
2. Develop interventions to the specific interests of elementary teachers and pupils in the Pili District. For teachers, prioritize discussions on planting and garden care, while encouraging their engagement in technology and attending training. For pupils, emphasize activities related to soil identification, agricultural planning, and hands-on care,

while fostering interest in technology through interactive training sessions.

3. To enhance agriculture teaching among elementary teachers in Pili District and foster pupil interest, it is important to address pupil-related factors (socio-economic status), curriculum-related issues (availability of teaching aids and textbooks), and resource-related factors (availability of materials, tools, and equipment). Additionally, support teachers with comprehensive guides to agricultural practices and allocate adequate time for practical work in the curriculum. Ensuring the availability of equipment for practical agricultural work is also essential.
4. Considering the significant relationships between the profile of teachers and their level of interest in specific aspects, as well as the profile of pupils and their level of interest, it is recommended to recognize and leverage individual characteristics and experiences when promoting interest in agriculture. Provide opportunities for teachers and pupils to share their experiences, collaborate with agricultural cooperatives, and integrate practical use of agricultural tools in both school and community settings. Tailoring initiatives based on individual profiles can foster a deeper engagement and enthusiasm for agriculture among teachers and pupils.
5. Foster collaboration and shared experiences between elementary pupils and teachers, emphasizing mutual learning and an inclusive environment. Encourage teamwork, exchange of ideas, and value

the diverse perspectives and knowledge of both groups to enhance agriculture education.

6. Addressing the primary concerns of elementary teachers in agriculture involves securing suitable land for planting and implementing agriculture school programs for pupils. Additionally, resolving minor issues like concept application, teacher involvement, recognition, incentives, technological awareness, trainings, financial capacity, and teaching aids will enhance the teaching and learning experience. For elementary pupils, prioritizing technological knowledge, cooperation, agricultural programs, practical application, and suitable planting areas will overcome their moderate challenges in agriculture education.
7. Foster open communication and shared experiences to collectively address challenges and create an inclusive and cooperative environment. This approach will enhance the effectiveness and holistic nature of agricultural education. The elementary pupils and teachers may attend and participate in various trainings, seminars and workshops on the basic concepts and practices in agriculture for them to be guided with necessary values and traits to become agriculture-literate.
8. Implement the proposed intervention programs in the Pili District to enhance agriculture education. Focus on providing formal trainings and seminars for teachers, allocating funds and resources, implementing school programs, and conducting parent orientations. For pupils, offer trainings in agricultural subjects, provide learning

materials and equipment, and collaborate with the local government for agricultural resources. These interventions aim to improve teaching and learning experiences, foster agricultural awareness, and enhance the overall quality of agriculture education in the district.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

Statistical tools formulas

Frequency Count. This was used to get the number of respondents in the conduct of the study.

Mean. This was used to determine the academic performance of the competency level of Grade 4 pupils.

Standard Deviation. This was used to determine the variability in the academic performance of the level of Grade 4 students. The formula is:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \bar{x}|^2}{n}}$$

where,

SD = Standard Deviation
 $\bar{x}$ = mean
x = score
n = number of case

where,

PL = Proficiency level
x = mean

Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation.

Formula

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where:

r= correlation coefficient
x₁= values of the x-variable in a sample
 $\bar{x}$ = mean of the values of the x-variable
y₁= values of the y-variable in a sample
 $\bar{y}$ = mean of the values of the y-variable

APPENDIX 1

Statistical tools formulas

Coefficient of Determination.

$$t = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{(s_1)^2}{n_1} + \frac{(s_2)^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where:

ΣD : Sum of the differences (Sum of X-Y from Step 2)

ΣD^2 : Sum of the squared differences (from Step 4)

$(\Sigma D)^2$: Sum of the differences (from Step 2), squared.

APPENDIX 2

Approved Request Letter to Schools Division Superintendent

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur 4418
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Email Address: op@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

November 3, 2022

LOIDA N. NIDEA, PhD
CESO V
Division of Camarines Sur

Dear Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a research study entitled "Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging "(A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning) in the fulfillment of her Master Thesis as major and final requirement for the degree in Master Science in Agricultural Education.

In view of this, may I have the honor to ask permission from your good office to administer the Survey questionnaires on selected pupils and Agriculture Teachers at Pili District, under your Division.

Rest assured, that the result and other information to be provided by the pupils and teachers will remain confidential and not in any way affect their reputation rather it will be used as basis to improve the teaching and learning of Agriculture subject.

Thank you and God bless.

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
MS AgEd Student
Researcher

Noted:

DR. CHARLIE P. NACARIO
Thesis Adviser
Professor VI

DR. CLARIBELLE C. HABER
Dean, Graduate School

APPENDIX 3

Approved Request Letter to Assistant School District Supervisor

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur 4418
Website: www.cbsua.edu.ph
Email Address: op@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

November 3, 2022

LYNN Z. PADILLO, PhD
Assistant Schools Division Superintendent
Division of Camarines Sur

Dear Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a research study entitled "Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging "(A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning) in the fulfillment of her Master Thesis as major and final requirement for the degree in Master Science in Agricultural Education.

In view of this, may I have the honor to ask permission from your good office to administer the Survey questionnaires on selected pupils and Agriculture Teachers at Pili District, under your Division.

Rest assured, that the result and other information to be provided by the pupils and teachers will remain confidential and not in any way affect their reputation rather it will be used as basis to improve the teaching and learning of Agriculture subject.

Thank you and God bless.

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
MS AgEd Student
Researcher

Noted:

DR. CHARLIE P. NAGARIO
Thesis Adviser
Professor VI

DR. CLARIBELLE C. HABER
Dean, Graduate School

APPENDIX 4

Approved Request Letter to Pili West, Public School District Supervisor

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur 4418
Website: www.cbsua.edu.ph
Email Address: op@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

August 8, 2022

IRENE E. MALATE, PhD
Pili West, Public Schools District Supervisor
Pili, Camarines Sur

Dear Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a research study entitled "Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging "(A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning) in the fulfillment of her Master Thesis as major and final requirement for the degree in Master Science in Agricultural Education.

In view of this, may I have the honor to ask permission from your good office to administer the Survey questionnaires on selected pupils and Agriculture Teachers at Pili District, under your Division.

Rest assured, that the result and other information to be provided by the pupils and teachers will remain confidential and not in any way affect their reputation rather it will be used as basis to improve the teaching and learning of Agriculture subject.

Thank you and God bless.

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
MS AgEd Student
Researcher

Noted:

DR. CHARLIE P. NACARIO
Thesis Adviser
Professor VI

DR. CLARIBELLE C. HABER
Dean, Graduate School

APPENDIX 5

Approved Request Letter to Pili East, Public School District Supervisor

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur 4418
Website: www.cbsua.edu.ph
Email Address: op@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

August 8, 2022

JENNELYN S. CEDRON, PhD
Pili East, Public Schools District Supervisor
Pili, Camarines Sur

Dear Madam:

Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a research study entitled "Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging "(A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning) in the fulfillment of her Master Thesis as major and final requirement for the degree in Master Science in Agricultural Education.

In view of this, may I have the honor to ask permission from your good office to administer the Survey questionnaires on selected pupils and Agriculture Teachers at Pili District, under your Division.

Rest assured, that the result and other information to be provided by the pupils and teachers will remain confidential and not in any way affect their reputation rather it will be used as basis to improve the teaching and learning of Agriculture subject.

Thank you and God bless.

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
MS AgEd Student
Researcher

Noted:

DR. CHARLIE P. NACARIO
Thesis Adviser
Professor VI

DR. CLARIBELLE C. HABER
Dean, Graduate School

APPENDIX 6

SURVEY INSTRUMENT VALIDATION SCALE

Adopted from Oducado RM (2020), Survey Instrument Validation Rating Scale.
Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3789575

Instructions: Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement on the statements provided below by encircling the number which corresponds to your best judgment

1-Strongly Disagree 2-Disagree 3-Undecided 4-Agree 5-Strongly Agree

AVERAGE OF RATINGS

CRITERIA	RATING					AVERAGE
The terms in the instrument are relevant to answer the objectives of the study.	1	2	3	4	5	3.8
The items in the instrument can obtain depth to construct being measured.	1	2	3	4	5	4.8
The instrument has appropriate sample of items for the construct measured.	1	2	3	4	5	4.6
The items and their alternatives are neither too narrow nor limited in their content.	1	2	3	4	5	4
The items in the instrument are stated clearly.	1	2	3	4	5	4.6
The items in the instrument can elicit response that are stable, definite, consistent, and not conflicting.	1	2	3	4	5	4.8
The terms adopted in the scale are culturally appropriate.	1	2	3	4	5	4.8
The layout or format of the instrument is technically sound.	1	2	3	4	5	4.8
The responses on the scale show a reasonable range of variation.	1	2	3	4	5	5

APPENDIX 6

SURVEY INSTRUMENT VALIDATION SCALE

The instrument is not too short or long enough that the participants will be able to answer it within a given time.	1	2	3	4	5	4.6
The instrument is interesting such that participants will be induced to respond to it and accomplish it fully.	1	2	3	4	5	3.8
The instrument as a whole could answer the basic purpose for which it is designed.	1	2	3	4	5	4.4
The instrument is culturally acceptable when administered in the local setting.	1	2	3	4	5	4.8
TOTAL RATING						4.52

Comments and Suggestions:

APPENDIX 7

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

ISO 9001:201
CERTIFIED

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur, 4418
Website:
Email Address:
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

PROJECT MATE:
MAKING AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING ENGAGING
(A PROGRAM INTERVENTION FOR ENHANCING ELEMENTARY
AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING)

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondents,

Good day!

This questionnaire will assess the interest in Agriculture of DepEd teachers and pupils in Pili District. Kindly go over this questionnaire and check the column that fits your answer. Be assured that all answers you provide will be kept with the utmost confidentiality.

Thank you.

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Researcher

Noted:

CHARLIE P. NACARIO Ph.D.
Thesis Adviser

Data Privacy Notice

The researcher respects your right to privacy and is committed to protecting the confidentiality of your personal information. It has adapted reasonable administrative, physical and technical measures to prevent the loss, misuse, and alteration of the information under our control. However, no method of transmission over the internet or method of electronic storage is 100% secure. By filling up this form you are consenting to the collection, processing, and use of the information in accordance with this privacy notice. The following information is collected and processed; respondent's name, age, gender, contact number, address, school, years in service and email address.

The information you have is used for any or all of the following: access provision, attendance, monitoring, evaluation, documentation, and communication purposes. The Information is collected and stored through Google; Google has its own Privacy Policy. Visit <https://www.google.com/policies/privacy/>. The researcher only retains the said personal information until it serves its purpose, after which it shall be securely disposed of. If you have concerns and queries on data Privacy, email rowena.agbulos@cbsua.edu.ph

I agree to this privacy notice

APPENDIX 7

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
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Website: www.cbsua.edu.ph
Email Address: ad@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

Part I. RESPONDENT'S PROFILE (TEACHERS):

Direction: Please check or write the appropriate answer in the space provided for:

Name of Respondent (Optional) _____

Name of School: _____

Address: _____

Date: _____

A. SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Sex:

Male Female

Age:

20 - 29 years old

30 - 39 years old

40 - 49 years old

50 - 59 years old

60 years above

Civil Status:

Single Solo Parent Married

Separated Widow /Widower

Highest Educational Attainment related to Agriculture

Bachelor's Degree with Agriculture Subject

Bachelor's Degree without Agriculture Subject

Post-Graduate degree level with Agriculture subjects

Post-Graduate degree level without Agriculture subjects

B. SOCIAL

Do you belong to a Farming Family?

Yes

No

Have you Inherit Agriculture Practices?

Yes, If yes if please specify:

Crop

Livestock

Fishing

No

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C. ECONOMIC

Employment:

- Permanent
 Locally Funded
 Volunteer

Position:

- Teacher I
 Teacher II
 Teacher III
 Master Teacher I
 Master Teacher II

Years in Service:

- <1 year - 10 years
 11 years - 20 years
 21 years - 30 years
 31 years and above

Nature of Appointment:

- Volunteer Teacher/Locally Funded Teacher/Substitute Teacher
 Permanent Teacher

Monthly Income:

- <P5,000.00- P15,000.00
 P15,001- P25,000.00
 P25,001- >35,000.00

Annual Agriculture related Income (if there is any):

- <P 5,000.00
 P 5,001.00 - P 10,000.00
 P 10,001.00- P 20,000.00
 P 20,001.00- P 30,000.00
 P 30,000 and above

D. CULTURAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN FARMING ADOPTED

Are you Practicing Traditional Beliefs/ Rituals in Farming?

- Yes
 No

If yes, please specify _____

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What kind of farming do you practice?

- Traditional / Organic Farming
 Modern Farming
 Combination of Traditional and Modern Farming

What kind of Agricultural Production do you engage/invest?

- Vegetables
 Fruits
 Livestock (Piggery/Poultry)
 None

Do you own a Farm Lot?

- Yes
 No

How big is your Farm Lot?

- < ½ ha
 ½ ha – 1 ha
 1.1 ha and above
 None

E. POLITICAL ENGAGEMENT PROFILE

Are you a member of an Agriculture Cooperative?

- Yes, please specify _____
 No

Have you been elected as Cooperative Agriculture Leader or Barangay Committee Head on Agriculture?

- Yes Please specify _____
 No

F. TECHNOLOGICAL RELATED SERVICES

Do you have access to Agriculture and Technology related services offered by the Barangay or School?

- Yes
 No

Are you using Technological Tools for Farming?

- Yes, if yes please specify: _____
 No

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Do you attend Agricultural Trainings?

Yes. Please specify: _____

No

Part II

Indicate your level of interest in agriculture by responding how frequently you apply or perform the following agriculture related activities whether in School or in the Community:

Agriculture Activities	Never	Rarely	Often	Always
Talk about the importance of planting /propagating trees with peers				
Use technological ways in improving ways of Planting and raising animals				
Identify the types of land that is applicable for propagating plants and raising animals.				
Prepares layout design before planting or animal to be raised.				
Use Manuals that guides proper ways of propagating plants and raising animals.				
Perform systematic ways of caring garden/plants seedling such as watering, cultivating, preparing, and applying organic fertilizer.				
Market Agricultural products				
Develops plan for improving the next production of planting and raising animals.				
Assist people in the problems arises in terms of Agriculture and help preventing the hazards.				
Attend training/seminar on Agriculture.				
Design project, implement plan and manages Agriculture Activities.				
Watch Agri T.V. programs and You Tube Channel				

Part III Factors affecting the teaching and Learning in Agriculture.

Please check the factors affecting the interest in Teaching Elementary Agriculture

A. Pupils related factors

- Socio economic status of the family
- Absenteeism of pupil
- Type of school previously attended

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Teaching materials
 Others, please specify _____

B. Factors Related to Curriculum Issues

- Coverage of subject content in Syllabus
 - Lessons plans
 - Available teaching aids
 - Textbooks
- Others, please specify _____

C. Resources related factor

- Student teacher ratio
 - Laboratory facilities
 - Availability of materials, tools and equipment
 - Area for practical application
- Others, please specify _____

Part IV.

Problems encountered by teacher and pupil in Agriculture. Kindly check the level of seriousness related to the problems encountered given below. Choose from 1 to 5, 5 being the most serious problem.

Problems encountered by teacher and pupil in Agriculture	Level of Seriousness				
	5	4	3	2	1
1. Lack of Financial Capacity					
2. Lack of appropriate land/area for planting					
3. Lack of Agriculture School Programs for Pupils					
4. Lack of recognition and incentives					
5. Lack of Concept Application					
6. Lack of Technological Awareness					
7. Multiple School Task					
8. Lack of Teacher's Involvement in Agriculture Subject					
9. Lack of Proper Trainings					
10. Lack of Teaching Aids					

APPENDIX 7

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Part V. Proposed Intervention Program. Kindly check the following Propose Intervention to be implemented in Making Agriculture teaching-learning engaging.

- Conduct Formal Trainings and Seminars in Agriculture
- Implementation of School Program for Agriculture
- Provision of Complete Teaching Aids in Agriculture.
- Solicit Agricultural Tools from the Stakeholders
- Allocate Funds from the MOOE for the Agriculture
- Conceptualize Lesson Plans for the Subject
- Provide Appropriate Laboratory Facilities for practical Application
- Make Available Agriculture Brochures/Fliers
- Social Media Campaign about Agriculture such as Tiktok/Vlog
- Parents Orientation on Urban Gardening
- Others, Please Specify _____

Please specify any information/ insights that are not captured in this questionnaire that you wish to include to make Agriculture Teaching -Learning Engaging:

Thank you very much!

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Researcher

APPENDIX 8

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY PUPILS

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur 4418
Website: www.cbsua.edu.ph
Email Address: cb@cbsua.edu.ph
Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

Part I. RESPONDENT'S PROFILE (PUPILS):

Direction: Please check or write the appropriate answer in the space provided for:

Name of Respondent (Optional) _____

Name of School: _____

Address: _____

Date: _____

Part I. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE:

Edad:

- () 9 -10 y/o
- () 11- 12 y/o
- () 13 y/o pataas

Katarian:

- () Lalaki () Babae

Baitang:

- () Grade IV
- () Grade V
- () Grade VI

B. SOCIAL

Ikaw ba ay nabibilang sa Pamilya ng Magsasaka?

- () Oo
- () Hindi

Anong uri ng pagkasaka ang ginagawa ng iyong Pamilya?

- () Pagtatanim ng mga gulay at Prutas
- () Paghahayupan
- () Pangangisda
- () Wala

C. ECONOMIC

Ano ang trabaho ng iyong ama?

- () Magsasaka
- () Hindi Magsasaka

Ano ang trabaho ng iyong ina?

- () Magsasaka
- () Hindi Magsasaka

APPENDIX 8

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 Email Address: csu@cbsua.edu.ph
 Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

Part II. Ipahiwatig ang iyong antas ng interes sa gawaing pang-Agrikultura kung gaano mo ba kadalas isinasagawa ang mga sumusunod na pang-Agrikulturang gawain.

Gawaing Pang Agrikultura	Hindi Kailanman	Bihira	Madalas	Palagi
Napag-uusapan ng mga kaibigan ang kahalagahan ng Pagtatanim at Pagpapadami ng Pananim				
Nakagagamit ng mga Pang Teknolohiyang Pamamaraan sa Pagtatanim				
Nakikilala ang ibat-ibang uri ng lupa na nararapat sa pagtatanim at pag-hahayupan)				
Nakapahahanda ng sariling disenyo para sa pagtatanim at pag-aalaga ng mga hayop				
Nakagagamit ng Manwal bilang gabay sa tamang pagpapadami ng tanim at pag-aalaga ng mga hayop.				
Naisasagawa ang tamang pamamaraan at pag-aalaga sa mga tanim kagaya ng mga bagong punla, pagdidilig, pagsasanyos and paglalagay ng pataba maging sa pag-aalaga ng mga hayop.				
Nakatutulong sa Sa Magulang sa Pagbebenta ng mga Produktong pang-Agrikultura				
Naruto na iba pang paraan na makatutulong sa susunod na produksyon sa pagtatanim at paghahayupan.				
Nakatutulong sa mga Ka-edad na malutes ang saliranan sa Pang-agrikulturang Gawain sa Paaralan				
Sumasali sa mga Pagsasanay tungkol sa mga Pang-Agrikultura na Kasanayan.				
Nakagagawa ng Plano at Naisasagawa ng Maayos ang mga Pagsasanay sa Pang-Agrikulturang Gawain.				
Nanonood ng mga Programang Pang-Agrikultura at lumalahok sa mga pagsasanay sa Agrikultura				
Naisasagawa ang mga Gawaing pang-Agrikultura				

APPENDIX 8

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY PUPILS

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Ano ang Pinagkakabitang ng iyong Pamilya?

- Pagsasakahan
- Hindi Pagsasakahan

D. CULTURAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN FARMING ADAPTED

Kaya ba ay mawroang lumang stasakahan?

- Oo
- Hindi

Anong uri ng Pang-Agrikulturang produksyon ang tinayang itinatagpuan?

- Pagtatanim (Gulay/Palay/Mais/Tubo at iba pa)
- Paghahayupan (Babuyan/Mamukan/Itik/Kambing at iba pa)
- Palaisdam

E. POLITICAL RELATED SERVICES

Ang tungang mayulang ba ay kasali sa Pang-Agrikulturang samahan O kooperatiba?

- Oo
- Hindi

F. TECHNOLOGICAL

Anong kagamitang pang-agrikultura ang ginagamit sa tinayang paaralan o komunidad?

- Lumang Kagamitan
- Modernong kagamitan
- Parchas

Samasali ka ba sa mga gawain pang Agrikultura sa Paaralan?

- Oo
- Hindi

APPENDIX 8

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY PUPILS

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 Trunkline: (054) 871-5531-33 local 101

Part III.

Mga kadahilanan na nakakaapekto sa pagkatuto ng mga mag-aaral sa Agrikultura
 Tsekan ang mga dahilan na nakakaapekto sa pagkawala ng interes ng mga mag-aaral sa pagkatuto sa Agrikultura

A. Kaugnay na kadahilananang Pang-Guro

- Kawilihan ng Guro sa Asignaturang Pang Agrikultura
- Gabay ng Guro sa pagsasagawa sa Agrikultura

B. Kaugnay na kadahilananang Pang-Kurikulum

- Lugar para sa pangkasanayang gawaing pang-agrikultura
- Takdang-oras na inilaan para sa kasamayang gawain o praktikal na gawain.

C. Kaugnay na kadahilananang mag-aaral

- Kagamitang pang teknolohikal gamit sa mag-aaral.
- Mga kagamitan para sa praktikal na gawaing kasanayan sa Agrikultura..

Part IV.

Problemanag kinakaharap ng Guro at Mag-aaral sa Asignaturang Agrikultura.
 Pumili sa Antas ng Kaseryusuhan mula sa bilang 1-5, 5 bilang pinaka seryosong antas.

Problemanag kinakaharap ng Guro at mag-aaral sa Asignaturang Agrikultura.	Antas ng Kaseryusuhan				
	5	4	3	2	1
1. Kawalan ng tamang lugar para sa pagtatanim					
2. Kakulangan ng mga Programang pang Agrikultura pra sa mga mag-aaral					
3. Kakulangan ng konsepto sa pagsasagawa ng natutunan/praktikal na gawain.					
4. Kakulangan sa kalamayan ng pang teknolohikal.					
5. Kakulangan sa Pakikiisa o pakikilahok sa asignaturang pang agrikultura					

APPENDIX 8

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ELEMENTARY PUPILS

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Part V.

Mga Mungkahi Ikaunlad sa Programang Pang-Agrikultura. Tsekan ang mga sumusunod na mungkahi na sa tingin mo makatutulong sa Ikaunlad ng Pagtuturo at Pagkatuto ng mag-aaral sa asignaturang Agrikultura.

- Pagsasagawa ng mga Pagsasamay sa Pang-Agrikulturang Asignatura
- Pagpapatupad ng Programang Pang Pampaaralan sa Asignaturang Agrikultura
- Pagtustos ng Kompletong Kagamitan sa Pag-aaral
- Manghingi sa mga Nanungkulan Pang-Agrikulturang Kagamitan
- Pagkakaalob ng mga Karagdagang Babasahin para sa Asignaturang Pang-Agrikultura
- Mga Patalastas o kampanya galing sa Social Media gaya ng Tiktok o Vlog

Maraming Salamat!

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Researcher

APPENDIX 9

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

ISO 9001:2015
CERTIFIED

Republic of the Philippines
CENTRAL BICOL STATE UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE
San Jose, Pili, Camarines Sur, 4418
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PROJECT MATE:
MAKING AGRICULTURE TEACHING LEARNING ENGAGING
(A PROGRAM INTERVENTION FOR ENHANCING ELEMENTARY
AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING)

October 8, 2022

Dear Sir,

Good day!

I am conducting a research as a course requirement in my Master's Degree. In connection with this, I would like to ask you as an expert in the field, to validate the questionnaire I made for this purpose. Please feel free to answer the survey instrument validation form. I would like to appreciate your assistance and support in this particular research endeavor.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Very truly yours,

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Researcher

Noted:

CHARLIE P. NACARIO Ph.D.
Thesis Adviser

Data Privacy Notice

The researcher respects your right to privacy and is committed to protecting the confidentiality of your personal information. It has adapted reasonable administrative, physical and technical measures to prevent the loss, misuse, and alteration of the information under our control. However, no method of transmission over the internet or method of electronic storage is 100% secure. By filling up this form you are consenting to the collection, processing, and use of the information in accordance with this privacy notice. The following information is collected and processed; respondent's name, age, gender, contact number, address, school, years in service and email address. The information you have is used for any or all of the following: access provision, attendance, monitoring, evaluation, documentation, and communication purposes. The Information is collected and stored through Google; Google has its own Privacy Policy. Visit . The researcher only retains the said personal information until it serves its purpose, after which it shall be securely disposed of . If you have concerns and queries on data Privacy, email

I agree to this privacy notice

APPENDIX 9

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

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CERTIFIED

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SURVEY INSTRUMENT VALIDATION RATING SCALE

Adopted from Oducado RM (2020), Survey Instrument Validation Rating Scale. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3789575

Instruction: Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement on the statements provided below by encircling the number which corresponds to your best judgment
 1-Strongly Disagree 2- Disagree 3- Undecided 4- Agree 5- Strongly Agree

CRITERIA	RATING				
The items in the instrument are relevant to answer the objectives of the study.	1	2	3	4	5
The items in the instrument can obtain depth to construct being measured.	1	2	3	4	5
The instrument has an appropriate sample of items for the construct measured.	1	2	3	4	5
The items and their alternatives are neither too narrow nor limited in their content	1	2	3	4	5
The items in the instrument are started clearly.	1	2	3	4	5
The items on the instrument can elicit responses that are stable, definite, consistent, and not conflicting.	1	2	3	4	5
The terms adopted in the scale in the scale are culturally appropriate	1	2	3	4	5
The layout or format of the instrument is technically sound.	1	2	3	4	5
The responses on the scale show a reasonable range of variation.	1	2	3	4	5
The instrument is not too short or long enough that the participants will be able to answer it within a given time.	1	2	3	4	5
The instrument is interesting such that participants will be induced to respond to it and accomplish it fully.	1	2	3	4	5
The instrument as a whole could answer the basic purpose for which is designed	1	2	3	4	5
The instrument is culturally acceptable when administered in the local setting.	1	2	3	4	5

Comments and Suggestions:

APPENDIX 10
PROJECT PROPOSAL

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Region V
Division of Camarines Sur
PILI EAST DISTRICT

PROJECT PROPOSAL

I. Program Title:	PROJECT MATE: <u>MAKING AGRICULTURE TEACHING LEARNING ENGAGING</u> (A PROGRAM INTERVENTION FOR ENHANCING ELEMENTARY AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING)	
II. Type	Regular	
III. Objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To enhance knowledge transfer and innovation in Agriculture. 2. Promotes competitiveness approach in Agriculture subject. 3. Encourage the continued development of learning and teaching within agriculture programs in collaboration of Department Agriculture and Department of Education 	
IV. District: PILI EAST DISTRICT	Division: CAMARINES SUR	
V. Beneficiaries:	Beneficiaries : Direct (Teachers of Pili East District)	GPP Coordinators of Pili East District
	Indirect (Pupils)	Intermediate Pupils
VI. Program Description	<p style="text-align: center;">PROJECT MATE: <u>MAKING AGRICULTURE TEACHING LEARNING ENGAGING</u> (A PROGRAM INTERVENTION FOR ENHANCING ELEMENTARY AGRICULTURE TEACHING-LEARNING)</p> <p>A strenuous task of encouraging not only the learners, as well as the teachers to cultivate their interest in Agriculture subject that encompasses an innovative learning, making the subject more valuable and edifying. An aid on how to become more efficient and effectively perform different roles through developing strategies, interventions and other instructional materials nurturing the interest of the learners in agriculture. Serves as guide in formulating interventions and developing new curriculum on how to increase the motivation of both teachers and pupils in teaching and learning in agriculture.</p>	
VII. Budget and Source Fund:	<p>The budget to be used for the procurement of the conduct of this training shall be shouldered by the proponent.</p> <p>Tarpaulin – 250 Certificates and Tokens – 1000 TOTAL - 1250</p>	
VIII. Source Fund:	Personal Funds	

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IX. Values	Commitment, Involvement and Innovation	
X. Competencies:	Competencies, Competencies that Need to be Enhanced, Enhancement Program, Level of Competency, Profile of Teachers, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE).	
XI. Mode of Delivery/Venue/Duration /Level of Management/	May 5,6 & 13, 2023 CBSUA Auditorium/Pili East District Office Orientation, Seminar, Training, Sharing, and Discussion Face to face	
XII. Output/s	Surveyed Questionnaires	
XIII. Organizational Outcome	Enhance teachers' knowledge in Agriculture subject and transfer to innovation that promotes and encourage continued development teaching-learning process	
XIV. Development Impact	Recognizes the need to enhance the knowledge and trainings of Elementary Teachers particularly for Agriculture Teachers to promote competitiveness in teaching-learning and engaging process.	
XV. Activities Briefly describe the Activity including The persons in charge Other resources needed, if any)	Pre – Implementation: 1, Consultation with the School Principal, School Head in Charge in Agriculture and PSDS 2. Planning 3. Orientation 4. Preparation and Submission of action plan 5. Information dissemination	
	Implementation Face to face: 1. Training needs to be Conducted including the schedule. Dates: May 5,6 & 13, 2023	Face to face/ Job Embedded Learning: Teachers take – away from the sessions attended and from topics presented that will help them in integrating the lessons in the elementary agriculture subject through enhancing knowledge and field application.
	Person Responsible: Schools GPP Coordinator of Pili East	
	Post Implementation: 1. Assessing answered surveyed questionnaire. 2. Providing Feedback	
XVI. Other Strategies	Request TA from: School Head and teachers	
XVII. Success Indicators:	1. Accomplishment Report 2. Monitoring Form 3. Surveyed Questionnaire	

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XVIII. Monitoring and Evaluation:	The 3-day District Seminar and Forum for teachers will be closely monitored by the PSDS Evaluation of this training shall be conducted by the teachers using the presented tool provided by the Resource Speakers
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Prepared by:

ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Proponent/ Researcher/Agriculture Teacher

ALDRIN B. BATALLER
Co-Proponent/District Agriculture-GPP Coordinator

Noted:

MARIJANE G. CEA
School Head-in-Charge in Agriculture/GPP

Approved:

CYRIL RARIZA SALAZAR, PhD
Public Schools District Supervisor

APPENDIX 10
PROJECT PROPOSAL

9:00- 10:30 AM	Overview of an Agriculture in the Philippines and Agriculture as subject in Elementary Paz P. Codilana San Jose South ES Pili West	Vermiculture Vermicomposting Juan Paulo Remoquillo Acopio TVET Trainer	Elementary Agricultural Education Programs Agricultural Problems and Management Aldrin B. Batailer Quirico Borja Sr. Memorial ES Pili East District GPP-Coordinator
10:30-12:00	Asexual Propagation Dish Gardening Rhizza Salditos Pamplona National High School	Organic Agriculture Basic Organic Vegetable Gardening Organic Fertilizer production and Concoctions Juan Paulo Remoquillo Acopio TVET Trainer	Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging (A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning) Rowena S. Agbulos Himaa ES Researcher
LUNCH BREAK			
12:00 – 1:00			
1:00 – 2:30 PM	Gulayan sa Paaralan Gulayan sa Tahanan Hazel Papillera G. Dumalasa ES, Calabanga East District	Introduction to Vegetable Gardening Urban Gardening Jinky E. Besinio Agricultural Technologist	Impression: Arnel B. Gomez Jose B. Velarde ES School GPP Coordinator Acceptance: Marijane G. Cea GPP School Head in Charge
2:30 – 4:00 PM	Animal Raising Livestock Production and the Functioning of Agricultural Ecosystem Maricres H. Berjuela Tinangis ES Pili West District	Cultural Management Practices (Land preparation, seedling establishment, transplanting, care of plants) Jinky E. Besinio Agricultural Technologist	Awarding of Certificates (Participants)

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PROJECT PROPOSAL

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
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 Division of Camarines Sur
 PILI EAST DISTRICT

Project MATE: Making Agriculture Teaching-Learning Engaging
 (A Program Intervention for Enhancing Elementary Agriculture Teaching-Learning)

March 5, 6 and 13, 2023 Pili East District

Time	Day 1 May 5, 2023 (Friday)	Day 2 May 6, 2023 (Saturday)	Day 3 January 13, 2023 (Saturday)
8:00 – 8:30	Registration	Arrival/Management of Learning	Arrival/Management of Learning
8:30 – 9:00	Preliminaries: Prayer(Audio Visual) Singing of Philippine National Anthem(AV) Checking of Attendance: Sheila P. Garbiles Words to Ponder: Aile C. Dela Torre Welcome Remarks: Rowena S. Agbulos Proponent Message: Marijean B. Cea Agriculture&GPP School Head in Charge Message: Cyril R. Salazar, PhD PSDS Pili-East Orientation of the Program: Rowena S. Agbulos	Preliminaries: Prayer: Audio Visual Checking of Attendance: Arnel Nollan Words to Ponder: Babilene R. Bascuna MOL: Shallymar V. Bagamasbad Message: Aldrin B. Bataler District Chief SGOD	Preliminaries: Prayer Audio Visual Checking of Attendance: Marife B. Israel Words to Ponder: Venus Ramirez MOL: Mercy T. Galicia Message: Dr. Charlie P. Nacario CBSUA Professor VI Adviser of the Proponent

APPENDIX 10
PROJECT PROPOSAL

4:00- 5:00 PM	Feedbacking and Evaluation	Feedbacking and Evaluation	Word of Thanks: Aldrin B. Bataler Co-Proponent Rowena S. Agbulos Proponent Moderator: Sheila P. Garbiles
	Moderator: Mary Corine D. Gargalicano	Moderator: Inigo A. Balbuena	

Prepared by :

Rowena S. Agbulos
ROWENA S. AGBULOS
Proponent

Aldrin B. Bataler
ALDRIN B. BATALER
Co-Proponent/GPP District Coordinator

Noted:

Marijane G. CEA
MARIJANE G. CEA
Agriculture & GPP School Head-in-Charge

Approved:

Cyril Rariza Salazar
CYRIL RARIZA SALAZAR, PHD
Public Schools District Supervisor

APPENDIX 11
PROPOSAL DEFENSE
July 29, 2022

APPENDIX 12
PRE-FINAL DEFENSE
January 28, 2023

APPENDIX 13

Oral Comprehensive Exam and Final Defense

March 13, 2023

APPENDIX 14

Consultation with Dr. Charlie P. Nacario and Sir Bryan Cariaga

APPENDIX 15
IMPLEMENTATION

